

Fig. S1| Immunofluorescence staining of CCR5+iNOS+ immunocytes in the control, control+CCL5, EAP, and EAP+CCL5 groups. Note: EAP, experimental autoimmune prostatitis;

Fig. S2| Comparisons of CCR1, CCR3, CCR4, and CCR5 expression between groups. Note: Data source from RNA sequencing analyses of control, EAP, EAP + CCL5, and EAP + Maraviroc samples. Note: EAP, experimental autoimmune prostatitis;

Table S1| Representative assay working ranges, sensitivity, and precision

Targets	Assay working	Assay sensitivity,	Assay precision, % ^b
	ranges, pg/mL ^a	pg/mL	
	LLOQ–ULOQ	LOD	standard curve CV
SCGF-beta	297.41-1426726.00	706	0
IL-9	7.45-34460.00	0	0
IL-17	10.56-47578.00	2	7.71
IL-12(p70)	7.29-31600.00	0	8.84
IL-7	10.76-56722.00	0	1.23
IL-15	72.86-286939.00	0	2.4
CTACK	5.60-23681.00	0	0
M-CSF	2.92-12315.00	1	1.15
TRAIL	3.65-10806.00	1	0
SCF	12.00-52939.00	1	7.25
IL-3	0.30-1563.00	0	2.11
IL-1alpha	14.38-60697.00	1	6.96
HGF	43.63-182737.00	6	1.06
GRO-alpha	89.33-452435.00	83	2.87
G-CSF	26.93-114249.00	4	2.11
IL-10	4.23-18014.00	0	1.75
MIP-1alpha	0.20-1025.00	0	16.64
IL-8	3.39-15725.00	1	6.09
MCP-1(MCAF)	2.12-9701.00	0	1.06
IL-4	1.23-5058.00	0	0
IL-13	0.90-3850.00	0	3.14
IP-10	6.46-27759.00	3	0
PDGF-BB	11.51-54843.00	3	4.81
beta-NGF	0.81-4539.00	1	1.43
VEGF	17.55-104116.00	43	2.18
Basic FGF	16.32-37511.00	0	10.35
Eotaxin	0.33-1589.00	0	0
IL-18	4.01-17537.00	0	2.18
IL-1beta	1.22-5045.00	0	3.87
IL-2	4.40-20246.00	1	1.66
RANTES	3.16-15868	3	0.35

TNF-alpha	15.00-63404.00	2	1.52
MIF	9.28-40528.00	5	0
GM-CSF	1.51-6950.00	0	0
IL-5	25.64-123255.00	40	0.6
TNF-beta	3.90-20112.00	1	1.83
LIF	17.23-75237.00	1	9.43
IL-12(p40)	59.37-257005.00	3	10.1
IL-16	6.11-26098.00	1	0
MCP-3	1.01-4201.00	0	7.07
IL-1ra	36.37-162671.00	3	1.79
SDF-1alpha	7.90-39022.00	0	0
IFN-gamma	4.26-18583.00	0	4.2
IFN-alpha 2	6.31-41113.00	0	9.43
IL-6	1.31-5954.00	0	0
MIP-1beta	1.81-8315.00	1	1.04
MIG	7.67-36017.00	0	6.33
IL-2R alpha	3.26-14566.00	0	3.07

Note: ^a. Assay range is LLOQ and ULOQ, calculated from boundary standard curve points.

^b. Data were generated using the magnetic workflow with the Bio-Plex Pro Wash Station, % CV is the value of CV corresponding to the sample mean and the standard curve.

Table S2| The expression levels of inflammatory cytokines between the HCs group and the CP-LS group

Variables	HCs group (n = 9)	CP-LS group (n = 24)	t/Z	P-value
SCGFbeta, pg/ml	29557.778 ± 14686.773	25466.458 ± 8560.518	0.958	0.345
IL9, pg/ml	873.156 ± 63.485	977.539 ± 80.405	-3.398	0.002
IL17, pg/ml	11.720 [11.720,12.120]	13.320 [12.520,14.140]	-3.78	< 0.001
IL12p70, pg/ml	4.170 [3.860,4.490]	3.860 [3.280,4.170]	1.374	0.173
IL7, pg/ml	18.760 [17.160,20.400]	20.400 [18.760,22.060]	-1.819	0.065
IL15, pg/ml	18.232 ± 3.678	16.110 ± 4.484	1.23	0.228
CTACK, pg/ml	394.448 ± 94.929	350.371 ± 117.112	0.98	0.335
MCSF, pg/ml	13.220 [11.680,14.660]	14.140 [12.470,15.240]	-0.525	0.611
TRAIL, pg/ml	18.966 ± 4.430	24.832 ± 8.790	-2.433	0.022
SCF, pg/ml	59.420 [55.790,66.300]	63.800 [55.790,76.780]	-0.606	0.557
IL3, pg/ml	0.120 [0.100,0.170]	0.150 [0.120,0.150]	-0.344	0.743
IL1alpha, pg/ml	12.140 [11.000,13.340]	11.000 [10.460,13.340]	0.263	0.807
HGF, pg/ml	136.157 ± 16.762	160.787 ± 24.724	-2.675	0.012
GROalpha, pg/ml	202.940 [175.950,239.050]	340.670 [262.090,402.480]	-2.91	0.004
GCSF, pg/ml	50.200 [48.250,52.170]	56.220 [48.250,60.370]	-1.435	0.155
IL10, pg/ml	5.090 [5.090,6.360]	5.710 [5.090,6.030]	-0.889	0.373
MIP1alpha, pg/ml	0.700 [0.650,0.790]	0.790 [0.700,0.890]	-1.678	0.090
IL8, pg/ml	3.490 [3.220,3.760]	3.490 [3.220,3.760]	0.283	0.787
MCP1MCAF, pg/ml	6.050 [5.620,6.500]	7.450 [6.050,8.470]	-1.859	0.064
IL4, pg/ml	2.420 [2.270,2.580]	2.810 [2.580,3.220]	-3.113	0.002
IL13, pg/ml	2.920 [2.480,3.140]	2.700 [2.280,3.140]	-0.081	0.951
IP10, pg/ml	176.223 ± 40.812	165.190 ± 49.831	0.575	0.569
PDGFBB, pg/ml	72.670 [35.330,150.210]	399.820 [282.710,565.450]	-3.921	< 0.001
betaNGF, pg/ml	0.100 [0.060,0.140]	0.100 [0.080,0.180]	-0.647	0.530
VEGF, pg/ml	0.649 ± 0.257	0.531 ± 0.267	1.109	0.276
Basic_FGF, pg/ml	35.130 [33.330,35.130]	36.920 [35.130,38.710]	-1.839	0.064
Eotaxin, pg/ml	30.033 ± 9.713	36.220 ± 10.321	-1.51	0.141
IL18, pg/ml	14.260 [11.480,22.330]	16.020 [10.060,24.310]	-0.243	0.824
IL1beta, pg/ml	2.330 [2.090,2.580]	2.390 [1.860,3.720]	-0.182	0.871
IL2, pg/ml	2.760 ± 0.361	2.478 ± 0.525	1.439	0.160

RANTES/CCL5, pg/ml	4877.000 [3095.000,5093.000]	5800.000 [5318.000,6057.000]	-2.547	0.011
TNFalpha, pg/ml	35.128 ± 5.996	34.232 ± 3.780	0.494	0.624
MIF, pg/ml	514.376 ± 108.967	773.700 ± 179.639	-3.935	< 0.001
GMCSF, pg/ml	1.640 [1.500,1.640]	1.640 [1.640,1.920]	-1.475	0.137
IL5, pg/ml	1.270 [0.930,1.550]	0.670 [0.220,1.140]	2.627	0.009
TNFbeta, pg/ml	777.786 ± 96.933	836.716 ± 67.061	-1.913	0.065
LIF, pg/ml	27.984 ± 4.549	27.958 ± 4.369	0.015	0.988
IL12p40, pg/ml	78.926 ± 5.454	83.822 ± 8.352	-1.583	0.124
IL16, pg/ml	45.930 [40.720,52.010]	49.470 [42.710,57.530]	-1.172	0.248
MCP3, pg/ml	1.160 [1.010,1.160]	1.160 [1.080,1.160]	-0.93	0.337
IL1ra, pg/ml	6.650 [5.120,7.830]	6.650 [5.600,7.830]	-0.081	0.951
SDF1alpha, pg/ml	1204.258 ± 171.549	1112.039 ± 154.387	1.436	0.161
IFNgamma, pg/ml	4.790 [4.540,5.310]	4.790 [4.540,5.580]	0.04	0.984
IFNalpha_2, pg/ml	8.780 [8.030,8.780]	8.780 [8.030,8.780]	0.04	0.983
IL6, pg/ml	0.760 [0.660,0.820]	0.820 [0.640,0.880]	-0.344	0.746
MIP1beta, pg/ml	230.787 ± 18.045	250.578 ± 14.760	-3.121	0.004
MIG, pg/ml	70.780 [49.280,98.070]	51.580 [41.610,60.960]	2.062	0.041
IL2R_alpha, pg/ml	20.970 [17.700,27.930]	25.310 [20.970,32.480]	-0.889	0.383

Abbreviation: CP-LS, chronic prostatitis like symptoms; HCs, healthy controls;
cm,centimeter; kg, kilogram; m, mouth; pg, picogram

Table S3| Differentially Expressed Genes between groups

Gene Symbol	logFoldChange	Average Expression	t	P-Value
EAP VS. CONTROL				
Cyp4f18	3.72113658	-1.1405618	20.5074839	2.64E-06
9430062P05Rik	2.278518984	-4.9278222	18.2644198	4.88E-06
Dock10	2.539868146	-1.8133225	16.4371636	8.52E-06
Tlr13	2.315141147	0.1890116	16.1310084	9.41E-06
Serpina3g	4.232847873	-0.4585941	14.7853541	1.49E-05
Siglece	3.549340671	-0.3466203	14.6846742	1.54E-05
Hck	2.64040264	0.48281534	14.5788343	1.60E-05
Fhad1	2.278092843	-5.0841631	14.3557623	1.74E-05
Ccr1	2.230238095	-0.351869	13.4355197	2.46E-05
Ciita	3.34084371	-0.1573558	13.2194924	2.68E-05
Pirb	2.947709359	-0.6371123	13.1644237	2.73E-05
Lair1	2.078628799	-2.388733	13.0599478	2.85E-05
Serpina3h	2.847394604	-0.6735908	12.8505162	3.10E-05
Havcr2	3.276581708	-1.8977927	12.8448966	3.11E-05
Mpeg1	3.162179246	2.9458031	12.570154	3.48E-05
Abcb4	2.222412646	-4.4839336	12.3575569	3.80E-05
Igtp	3.603806561	1.16578865	12.1247519	4.20E-05
Dnaic2	2.914167777	-5.3479981	12.0001301	4.43E-05
Slc11a1	2.26187406	-0.3414643	11.8228126	4.79E-05
Cd300a	1.959568328	-1.7367412	11.748866	4.95E-05
Cd74	3.601948974	6.23365089	11.6776089	5.11E-05
Pla2g7	2.003716233	1.56098453	11.5505034	5.40E-05
H2-Ab1	4.09926433	3.67072141	11.4179725	5.74E-05
Vcam1	2.305466117	0.88610779	11.4088063	5.76E-05
Ly86	2.672315086	2.35140085	10.9901027	6.99E-05
Fcgr2b	1.925454196	-0.1550619	10.914007	7.25E-05
Bambi-ps1	2.773722908	-2.1818831	10.8564621	7.45E-05
Tbc1d10c	2.564756807	-0.1229574	10.8422197	7.50E-05
Adrg5	3.364982369	-2.0639783	10.7761969	7.74E-05
Fyb	2.446605257	0.29970067	10.6120985	8.38E-05
A530032D15Rik	2.146194362	-1.8546528	10.3753002	9.41E-05
Adap2	2.514846084	0.96734101	10.3314038	9.62E-05
Rasa13	2.69099244	-2.064575	10.2135684	0.000102
Vav1	2.461035815	-0.2749983	10.212829	0.000102
Itgb7	3.099374553	0.39140589	10.0896647	0.0001086
Lyz2	2.128343058	6.6840177	10.0428641	0.0001112
P2ry10	3.943640856	-3.1115403	10.0375801	0.0001115
Amica1	3.618326829	0.62922015	10.0268926	0.0001121
Tap1	1.447133892	1.23604825	10.0112747	0.000113
Slc15a3	2.698776083	-1.746154	9.9658082	0.0001157

AU020206	1.548351619	2.23340139	9.90056039	0.0001197
Cybb	2.299376409	1.25553862	9.87263255	0.0001214
H2-DMb2	3.908771984	0.23841681	9.84433664	0.0001232
Cxcr3	3.228981247	-0.6476193	9.67735952	0.0001345
Ighj1	1.171163566	0.49837013	9.65011572	0.0001364
Icos	4.86018238	-3.708509	9.62716693	0.0001381
Klhl6	2.09649213	-0.8171734	9.55973882	0.0001432
Lcp2	2.191607483	-0.8850794	9.5589354	0.0001432
Pik3r6	2.145160612	-1.3725735	9.5305043	0.0001454
Plek	1.878793952	0.07617148	9.42157504	0.0001542
Tnfaip8l2	1.728674389	1.19956645	9.38380668	0.0001574
Rinl	1.717598116	-0.0214691	9.36517912	0.000159
Tmigd1	2.275876025	-3.5416924	9.34588222	0.0001607
Itgam	2.143415993	0.85298698	9.32670055	0.0001624
Ctss	2.75838355	4.12442726	9.31959047	0.000163
Cd8a	3.923471656	-4.9736798	9.26966235	0.0001675
Ms4a6b	3.374085734	-0.6683876	9.25711649	0.0001687
Igsf6	2.588079817	-0.2147651	9.24314906	0.00017
Apobec1	2.165150085	0.67355413	9.20405325	0.0001737
Snx20	2.251200994	0.46331604	9.17522338	0.0001765
Ighm	5.618192267	4.20529642	9.1734797	0.0001767
Adgre1	2.83458976	2.28693921	9.11553899	0.0001825
Lst1	3.673947431	0.41690604	9.11190877	0.0001828
Inpp5d	2.136718105	-0.3978987	9.08987014	0.0001851
Wdfy4	2.753749152	-0.443767	9.05485475	0.0001888
Dnah8	1.653719568	-3.1569141	9.04702298	0.0001896
Tlr8	2.29653998	-1.4162	9.02544006	0.0001919
Gm10416	1.863022741	-1.7604739	9.01836141	0.0001927
Hvcn1	2.64099789	-0.3837308	8.99554384	0.0001952
Cnr2	2.752283414	-2.0789982	8.94501115	0.0002008
Prex1	1.644548736	-0.0487922	8.94468102	0.0002009
Fgd2	2.215288304	-0.1514893	8.78848353	0.0002196
Ighg1	9.570787814	2.76987744	8.74432139	0.0002253
H2-Eb1	4.293991511	5.35009196	8.7418222	0.0002256
Nckap1l	2.380189143	1.53957957	8.73356581	0.0002267
H2-Aa	3.881235886	3.90249603	8.71471091	0.0002292
Ccdc88b	2.79430383	-0.3815322	8.66588414	0.0002358
Clec7a	1.754605985	-0.2592793	8.65955061	0.0002367
Ms4a7	2.87893242	-0.8264962	8.6222894	0.0002419
Rac2	3.565716301	1.33353711	8.61809092	0.0002425
Nfam1	1.769785977	-0.3149962	8.61567976	0.0002428
Tnfrsf13b	3.591699233	-1.8264234	8.5904184	0.0002465
Sell	3.811610268	-3.9917034	8.58228771	0.0002476
Btla	3.850699136	-1.9728538	8.55621866	0.0002515
Rltpr	2.588339638	-2.1980921	8.54422698	0.0002533
Gbp5	3.029888758	-1.2568704	8.52382216	0.0002563

Pld4	2.171516474	2.84215587	8.46784733	0.000265
Laptm5	2.233281223	2.10700887	8.43865518	0.0002697
Bcl2a1b	2.761697183	0.57377057	8.40245537	0.0002756
Gm20427	1.549115167	2.64512764	8.37686701	0.0002798
C1qb	2.476886484	4.97318796	8.31286176	0.0002908
Ptprc	3.021691943	-0.6301036	8.31195666	0.000291
Chac1	-3.030392245	4.76867077	-8.2943663	0.0002941
Irgm2	3.029360859	0.97251394	8.24827274	0.0003025
Batf2	1.398968831	-3.1472106	8.2444573	0.0003032
Fcer1g	2.63931064	1.54246497	8.21209104	0.0003092
Gm14548	1.62976864	-1.680919	8.17228706	0.0003169
Chil1	4.072060905	-3.4451569	8.15644938	0.00032
Pik3r5	3.82572644	-0.575379	8.15564548	0.0003201
Ncf1	2.405777142	0.25270451	8.081934	0.0003351
Skap1	3.855971391	-4.7970389	8.0229334	0.0003476
Itgb2	2.524975491	1.31095062	8.00971636	0.0003505
C1qc	2.232750848	4.17891588	8.00775596	0.0003509
Btk	2.16584347	-0.7344422	7.98660179	0.0003556
Coro1a	2.656898605	0.9317253	7.9650296	0.0003604
Sla	3.734372436	-1.7806011	7.94415084	0.0003652
Ptpn7	2.710392631	-2.4361072	7.92819707	0.0003689
H2-DMb1	3.542579368	0.41478767	7.91025327	0.0003731
Tlr9	2.956370402	-0.6494264	7.89091666	0.0003777
Card11	4.277517941	-2.1140041	7.86411411	0.0003841
Fgd3	1.766692059	-0.8932569	7.8599903	0.0003852
Pmaip1	2.762566233	-0.8539074	7.85206539	0.0003871
Psemb9	1.40591902	1.26056071	7.83560916	0.0003912
Was	3.102153047	-0.280006	7.77372265	0.000407
Podnl1	3.700498464	-2.8563156	7.74013728	0.0004158
Clec4a2	3.171275024	-0.7783922	7.6430951	0.0004428
Cd274	2.17232381	0.11735968	7.63826117	0.0004442
Ppp1r18	1.483949454	0.25124842	7.63681617	0.0004446
C1qa	2.252308112	5.62134521	7.60282047	0.0004546
Cxcr6	3.214083067	-1.7569217	7.58303342	0.0004605
Slpi	5.644334693	1.17801458	7.55608804	0.0004687
H2-Q7	4.181138252	0.17940599	7.51260482	0.0004824
Fcho1	1.898343296	-1.7019576	7.5012105	0.000486
H2-DMa	2.707363455	1.76862962	7.49609091	0.0004877
Arl11	2.050590895	-0.8102438	7.49230805	0.0004889
Dennd1c	2.573160834	-0.3198499	7.48133087	0.0004925
Arhgap19	1.452091189	-0.5058425	7.42293942	0.000512
Parp14	1.091577931	1.94363861	7.39762663	0.0005207
Tgtp2	3.971764914	0.14621229	7.37384381	0.0005291
Gsap	1.75106358	-2.3768242	7.36827451	0.000531
Il18rap	2.604050984	-2.0925898	7.35664106	0.0005352
Sifn8	2.696150731	-1.5369802	7.29991474	0.0005561

Lrp8	1.588750534	-4.0697904	7.27058316	0.0005673
Sesn2	-1.256428477	3.15858589	-7.2326803	0.0005821
Hmha1	2.170275243	0.75217052	7.21429139	0.0005894
Lilr4b	1.71473156	-0.1149285	7.18312812	0.0006022
Arhgap4	2.231886933	-1.6181076	7.15008536	0.000616
Apobr	1.614948532	-0.5141203	7.1430302	0.000619
Il4ra	1.55835789	0.50524972	7.12746117	0.0006257
C1d	-1.078163105	2.0726243	-7.1221474	0.000628
Csf2rb	2.290067431	0.49030385	7.11309036	0.0006319
Gm15931	2.661402618	0.57461816	7.10306878	0.0006363
Arhgap30	2.804273882	-0.3650446	7.02140316	0.0006735
Syt13	1.113225982	-1.2901922	7.01825931	0.000675
Slamf8	3.141018597	-1.4820203	7.01686084	0.0006757
Lat2	2.091971145	-1.1062091	6.99307029	0.000687
Spi1	2.119115613	0.63403094	6.96982663	0.0006983
Tbxas1	2.248394646	-1.3699979	6.96796401	0.0006993
Lrrc25	2.013764799	0.96208624	6.95369275	0.0007063
Pik3cd	1.648754048	-0.7505211	6.94259062	0.0007119
Cd48	2.709598799	0.62115113	6.93463152	0.0007159
9930111J21Rik2	1.871614751	-1.1499204	6.92357343	0.0007215
Pim1	1.11779548	1.84445711	6.92351487	0.0007215
H2-Q4	1.613767622	3.75967919	6.89238109	0.0007376
Selplg	2.572751073	0.1688912	6.8681791	0.0007504
Syk	2.472530898	-0.2759781	6.86785731	0.0007506
Pyhin1	3.845194634	-2.7886432	6.86783293	0.0007506
Bcl11b	3.428385343	-4.3851686	6.85671303	0.0007566
Ncf2	1.74436655	-1.3029957	6.85037748	0.00076
Hcls1	2.487112583	1.59941213	6.84698339	0.0007619
Clec4a1	3.188385683	1.24711232	6.84350787	0.0007638
Smt3h2-ps	-0.828829653	-1.9280628	-6.8293954	0.0007715
Cx3cr1	1.986577338	0.35018818	6.82710094	0.0007728
Lilrb4a	1.987758492	0.81292769	6.80229196	0.0007866
Fmnl1	2.296102766	0.3403565	6.79347316	0.0007916
Fam105a	1.49618892	0.49502165	6.78880415	0.0007943
Cd79a	5.736000328	-0.8046985	6.77305292	0.0008034
Gbp6	2.427967572	-0.8167501	6.76221736	0.0008097
Plcb2	2.436614995	-2.278514	6.75955658	0.0008112
Akna	2.014893526	0.82754869	6.72337301	0.0008327
C3ar1	2.295662967	0.66366213	6.68625348	0.0008555
Atp8b4	2.552025551	-2.9137107	6.64185363	0.0008837
Itgal	3.297322924	-1.454534	6.63596464	0.0008875
Gm4951	4.025347596	-2.7154216	6.62244532	0.0008963
Napsa	3.832308725	-0.5095772	6.60783018	0.000906
Ncf4	2.609150166	-0.0647048	6.6047053	0.0009081
Gm4759	2.687794227	-0.8329257	6.60140347	0.0009103
Gm1966	3.266046513	-1.6844131	6.58859379	0.0009189

Il21r	3.237217418	-1.4296803	6.55392303	0.0009427
Kctd12	1.25357328	2.64022313	6.54925941	0.000946
Gimap3	3.718112229	-0.8081768	6.54737093	0.0009473
Slamf6	3.791905804	-3.7886043	6.52766814	0.0009613
Il16	1.818189495	-1.022472	6.51337496	0.0009715
Gpsm3	1.580121193	0.52426127	6.49493305	0.0009849
Cd72	3.520413401	-1.3668165	6.48645406	0.0009912
Gm42590	-1.096017621	-0.7679386	-6.4696991	0.0010037
Slc25a53	1.181071833	-2.4552291	6.43974794	0.0010265
Psmb8	2.237598212	2.31366063	6.43710865	0.0010285
Cd22	4.650020953	-3.130352	6.42657635	0.0010367
AW112010	3.503205295	1.77300323	6.41020799	0.0010495
Wfdc17	1.893035146	2.41068021	6.39975712	0.0010578
Myo1g	2.676387238	-0.8822436	6.39307736	0.0010632
C5ar1	1.65974636	0.3853199	6.37378345	0.0010788
Dok3	2.168614076	0.80119644	6.3725461	0.0010798
Tnfrsf14	1.423706591	0.73424999	6.37171328	0.0010805
Oas1b	1.251037478	1.21283117	6.36159388	0.0010888
Ppp1r16b	1.310319454	-1.22687	6.35781819	0.0010919
ligp1	4.19071635	1.29043245	6.3563101	0.0010931
5830432E09Rik	1.426423227	-4.1797397	6.33731804	0.001109
Cyth4	2.094578589	2.25361772	6.33127626	0.0011141
Lfng	1.543740936	1.2779301	6.31539791	0.0011277
Tnfrsf1b	1.400851275	1.75610179	6.30790416	0.0011342
Myo1f	2.450430072	0.01504296	6.2958485	0.0011446
Ifi47	3.852029981	-0.428246	6.27935324	0.0011592
Adam8	2.280766188	-1.5276329	6.27876385	0.0011597
Gpr65	3.15651674	-0.4222956	6.27614882	0.001162
Ms4a6c	3.185245696	1.60339104	6.27275843	0.001165
Bach2	2.85022734	-3.9203182	6.27091561	0.0011667
Ltb	2.689644009	-1.2725158	6.27008273	0.0011674
Tnfsf8	3.588570709	-3.2638468	6.26194065	0.0011748
Rftn1	1.396188114	-0.0684124	6.2342944	0.0012
Sash3	2.83414808	0.01710345	6.21904007	0.0012142
Themis2	2.675873471	0.66003442	6.21486372	0.0012181
Mir142hg	3.005706344	-0.3994143	6.21424976	0.0012187
Gm37886	2.422832336	-3.7110713	6.21365942	0.0012192
Ms4a6d	3.070617793	0.81282169	6.19584967	0.0012361
Gm11131	1.555940094	-1.6878471	6.19148951	0.0012403
Fxyd5	1.167227783	0.78849681	6.18495111	0.0012466
Nod2	0.710253528	-1.0139067	6.18475973	0.0012468
Map4k1	2.441564825	-0.015505	6.17801562	0.0012533
RP23-250E1.9	2.385604578	-2.0472612	6.17460869	0.0012567
Gm15753	1.297694089	0.38094165	6.17266072	0.0012586
Gm12735	2.13992365	-2.3022963	6.16781075	0.0012633
Lpxn	1.813251612	0.54002035	6.15210113	0.0012788

Irgm1	2.156894852	1.59715723	6.13933576	0.0012916
Msr1	1.947888293	-0.8710557	6.13308691	0.0012979
Tgtp1	4.581430358	-0.8507349	6.11769616	0.0013136
9130208D14Rik	2.094610516	-3.9488287	6.11264112	0.0013188
Mzb1	7.325725508	0.14871207	6.10310334	0.0013287
Apbb1ip	2.144567931	-0.8908156	6.09417714	0.001338
Fermt3	2.334662229	1.33618774	6.09403613	0.0013382
Dok1	1.334682556	0.30665272	6.08639537	0.0013462
Ccr2	2.353297622	-1.037304	6.08394022	0.0013488
Il27ra	2.546953294	-1.3388772	6.08235857	0.0013505
Traf3ip3	2.947323391	-3.2093267	6.06333975	0.0013709
Ifi203	2.549949739	-0.3415066	6.05503296	0.0013799
Mns1	2.449748334	-4.2867043	6.03622774	0.0014005
Stat1	1.873050737	1.33071462	6.03022724	0.0014071
Srgn	1.371690203	1.92733878	6.01786152	0.001421
Hk3	2.388882114	-1.3071023	5.9897517	0.001453
Lrp11	0.870728185	-0.6872163	5.98617038	0.0014572
Arhgap25	1.616738321	-1.0811823	5.98190499	0.0014621
Gm8995	2.61055033	0.02753703	5.95066321	0.001499
Clec4b1	3.74433561	-1.537871	5.94503407	0.0015057
Ifitm1	0.930685077	2.98290765	5.94080519	0.0015108
Arhgap9	1.896247455	0.65391116	5.92944342	0.0015246
Pkib	4.189478147	-5.656227	5.88752907	0.0015769
Ppfia4	1.634698045	-1.9641632	5.87413654	0.001594
Nlrc5	4.250870267	-0.9490811	5.87350332	0.0015948
Acap1	4.529854685	-2.6415926	5.86745723	0.0016026
Cd40	2.413585007	-2.7655689	5.8628566	0.0016086
St8sia4	1.433043614	-2.2147518	5.85947616	0.001613
Fcgr3	1.389474426	1.00052329	5.85869507	0.001614
Il7r	3.589201807	-2.2933748	5.85499642	0.0016188
2700046G09Rik	0.888642821	0.38561533	5.85206167	0.0016227
Itga4	2.562765922	-1.0982085	5.85068093	0.0016245
Tifab	2.287936172	-0.22306	5.84846329	0.0016274
Eif4ebp1	-0.979027133	5.99651006	-5.841795	0.0016362
Tyrobp	2.150955449	3.81729807	5.83512607	0.0016451
Lyl1	1.410349412	0.92848157	5.82775518	0.0016549
C920025E04Rik	0.847462793	2.38977725	5.8199516	0.0016655
Cd53	2.715301614	2.09748994	5.81555833	0.0016714
Igkc	8.41858943	5.58500545	5.80952651	0.0016796
Fam78a	3.657784104	-3.4809497	5.80409207	0.0016871
Relt	3.105887689	-2.3272628	5.80074235	0.0016917
Hpgds	1.713338538	-1.3425388	5.79811006	0.0016953
Cyba	1.355008643	3.82033648	5.78884418	0.0017082
Bin2	3.70691093	-1.1988215	5.78241908	0.0017172
Gimap4	1.814926675	-0.0988617	5.77059473	0.0017338
Stat4	3.598909078	-3.4297976	5.74718582	0.0017674

Jchain	7.723990938	1.53982321	5.73894901	0.0017794
Rhoh	3.617391806	-4.2380061	5.73741021	0.0017817
Mipol1	-0.654898817	-1.7562647	-5.7292257	0.0017937
Gbp2b	5.625671653	-1.2857703	5.72131045	0.0018054
Tlr1	2.589527829	-1.0282809	5.71838112	0.0018098
Al607873	1.623875058	0.55737176	5.71221952	0.001819
Tmem106a	1.273538586	0.11678032	5.70635261	0.0018278
Lrmp	2.448259506	-1.0521376	5.70311956	0.0018327
Kcnu1	-1.027591821	-2.7895967	-5.6850505	0.0018602
Ly9	4.054870354	-2.1190506	5.67103264	0.001882
Rassf4	1.61820929	1.20581882	5.66990245	0.0018837
Oasl1	1.214503783	-1.0640581	5.66735432	0.0018877
H2-Q6	4.029464842	1.8519505	5.66433501	0.0018924
Ikzf1	2.573204802	-1.6898209	5.64834993	0.0019177
Evi2b	2.587801398	0.32883703	5.64679339	0.0019202
Jakmip1	1.783745037	-3.9042884	5.63617387	0.0019373
Itgb3	0.852127061	0.08302585	5.63469559	0.0019396
Trim30a	2.149533992	0.15956434	5.61864506	0.0019658
Il2rb	4.253064875	-1.371283	5.61286631	0.0019753
Xcr1	4.191385043	-3.1889253	5.60499119	0.0019883
Cd180	2.439365914	-1.7995176	5.5909175	0.0020119
Cd79b	3.891110305	-0.859127	5.58938922	0.0020145
Gbp8	4.074707786	-2.2985062	5.58470268	0.0020224
Ccl8	5.511145222	2.93533376	5.57310369	0.0020422
Tspan32	3.069156873	-2.6650354	5.55476301	0.0020739
Arhgef6	1.231101669	0.04455148	5.54678505	0.0020879
Cd38	1.851263434	0.45529326	5.54284779	0.0020948
Aldh1b1	1.058383134	-0.0886701	5.52711412	0.0021228
Bcl2a1d	3.04911976	0.8455655	5.52361409	0.0021291
Ptprcap	4.333994615	-0.5842589	5.5205437	0.0021347
BC035044	2.385760168	-2.0825762	5.52026595	0.0021352
Cd68	1.38096845	2.48887905	5.5179035	0.0021394
Nup210	0.843004415	-0.0640759	5.50337421	0.0021659
Cytip	1.616499174	-0.3436926	5.49879609	0.0021743
Csf2ra	0.972694174	2.80663388	5.49582387	0.0021798
Grap	1.584869949	0.67032214	5.48831678	0.0021938
Adcy7	1.638287068	1.24517644	5.46310788	0.0022413
Aoah	3.443422141	-1.7240315	5.44300674	0.0022801
Sp110	1.287072831	-1.0734517	5.44133179	0.0022834
Cotl1	1.888220084	2.66471087	5.4274724	0.0023106
Gbp4	2.74025046	-0.3690942	5.39667665	0.0023725
Fes	0.975096062	-0.0874051	5.38957186	0.0023871
Jak3	1.790430838	-0.1756774	5.36867451	0.0024304
Ccr5	2.900158061	-0.5324946	5.33834127	0.0024951
Klrb1b	2.441027322	-1.9452996	5.33181923	0.0025092
Arhgap15	2.282597344	-2.6736469	5.32854974	0.0025164

Lmnb1	1.156883397	1.21687297	5.32659861	0.0025206
Il18bp	2.029417875	2.26221543	5.31685085	0.0025421
Gm28177	1.93437516	1.01980587	5.3060313	0.0025661
Cxcl9	5.935475982	-0.0575496	5.30010009	0.0025794
Fcgr1	3.18591226	-0.3575955	5.29108911	0.0025997
Slc13a3	4.05079464	-4.3715376	5.27721962	0.0026314
Abi3	1.798824214	-1.081482	5.27567083	0.002635
Gm9947	1.837828034	-5.2569609	5.26930262	0.0026497
Cd28	4.248023286	-4.1026711	5.26149226	0.0026679
Spn	3.424019094	-1.0109843	5.26137588	0.0026682
Plbd1	3.204295619	1.24517465	5.25059254	0.0026935
Pip4k2a	1.719499854	1.50804657	5.24230638	0.0027132
Ms4a4a	1.95305097	0.67445539	5.23296607	0.0027355
B3gnt5	2.262278259	-4.2807893	5.21772169	0.0027725
Cd86	2.194023345	-0.8067078	5.21702113	0.0027742
Frat2	0.744128375	-0.313713	5.20927341	0.0027932
Lin7a	1.348533482	-2.5261638	5.20450188	0.002805
Gm6034	2.329941544	-2.426575	5.20298634	0.0028088
Arhgap27os1	2.063383265	-1.8439918	5.19541101	0.0028277
Fam26f	3.664111341	-1.0753401	5.19248438	0.002835
C3	2.171331781	5.15086521	5.1859745	0.0028514
Gm5431	2.333986272	-2.9867659	5.18122317	0.0028634
Med1	0.616667863	2.08531579	5.17696607	0.0028742
Fgl2	1.426653322	3.14056446	5.16571219	0.002903
Cxcl13	3.920572217	3.31411763	5.15671358	0.0029263
Irf9	1.169611222	2.19809213	5.1505776	0.0029423
Gbp2	2.683059218	2.09095331	5.14600201	0.0029543
C130026l21Rik	1.53931607	-2.8728553	5.14560777	0.0029554
Unc93b1	1.000892118	3.70080711	5.14358728	0.0029607
Tespa1	3.388729072	-2.8626749	5.13188961	0.0029917
Ptger4	1.434613465	-0.8165992	5.13134237	0.0029932
Nfkbid	2.34110087	-2.9498626	5.12800053	0.0030021
AB124611	2.460171381	-0.9191137	5.12739895	0.0030037
Tcirg1	0.667564254	1.9845281	5.12451773	0.0030115
Pstpip1	2.259247604	-1.6964479	5.11977727	0.0030243
Cysltr1	0.740586398	-1.5927831	5.11888022	0.0030267
Irf5	2.095137155	0.51670576	5.11192193	0.0030456
Wipf1	1.057303904	0.59964617	5.10549687	0.0030631
Mafb	1.332144583	2.12590996	5.09347361	0.0030963
Csf1r	1.261726658	2.96823207	5.08731057	0.0031135
Csf3r	2.755708552	-1.5216983	5.0653948	0.0031754
Lag3	3.373240158	-1.512963	5.05721503	0.0031989
Kif21b	1.871445653	-0.9872824	5.05363372	0.0032092
C1qtnf3	1.176052501	-0.302241	5.04720755	0.0032279
Fam49a	0.820804002	1.19866839	5.04699406	0.0032285
Rhbdl3	1.161484696	-0.7064436	5.04274785	0.0032409

Dennd4b	1.064916683	0.43720473	5.03377297	0.0032673
Cbfa2t3	0.859451081	-0.9058236	5.0227885	0.0032999
Il2rg	2.337920773	0.24042002	5.01321171	0.0033287
Il10ra	1.937188134	-0.2595061	5.00741823	0.0033462
Lax1	3.735797255	-0.9905536	5.00170514	0.0033636
Clec4a3	3.01413642	0.39943073	4.98743862	0.0034075
Irf8	0.895535055	1.77776407	4.97921594	0.0034332
Rgs14	2.810140352	-1.7811283	4.97833472	0.0034359
Tpst2	0.740524984	1.67810842	4.96530895	0.003477
Al662270	2.825549691	0.19883466	4.95543141	0.0035085
Ptpn6	0.716210636	2.76438567	4.9464634	0.0035374
F730311O21Rik	1.497146256	-2.4622811	4.94227475	0.003551
Gm29170	0.935853981	-1.8617777	4.94184172	0.0035524
Grap2	4.510586992	-2.2420907	4.93631241	0.0035704
Ebi3	2.867236237	-0.6202664	4.91277367	0.0036484
Epsti1	2.810620041	-0.1343434	4.90002732	0.0036915
H2-Q1	1.478994047	-0.8827184	4.88485354	0.0037435
Agap2	1.325800572	-0.5173731	4.8815407	0.003755
Ighv9-1	7.7135195	0.49786002	4.87193168	0.0037885
Sh2d2a	4.183057325	-4.8200684	4.86935157	0.0037975
Sugct	-0.634781319	0.16082267	-4.8653695	0.0038115
Runx3	2.798348793	-2.4136348	4.86151457	0.0038252
Rcsd1	1.974957275	-0.988276	4.83558592	0.0039183
Gpr35	2.220935936	-3.7231205	4.82903369	0.0039423
Tm6sf1	1.589237405	-0.7263528	4.82813573	0.0039456
1700084C06Rik	-0.843959359	-1.0144965	-4.8220134	0.0039681
Serpina3i	2.656323692	-2.3690232	4.80346746	0.0040374
St6gal1	1.759664286	0.12964671	4.80251621	0.004041
Al317395	2.107165386	-4.8545304	4.79487531	0.0040699
Pde1b	1.941612764	-1.174773	4.79136502	0.0040833
Sipa1	1.065266184	2.04178946	4.75278813	0.0042338
F630028O10Rik	2.162612899	-3.2865715	4.75253105	0.0042348
Zfp444	-0.715274989	0.8499367	-4.7504036	0.0042433
Ada	1.29760867	0.18843945	4.74398477	0.004269
Clec12a	4.557390095	-1.9497681	4.74391626	0.0042693
Ccl2	2.103468551	-0.853955	4.73918871	0.0042883
Msn	1.000396333	3.09737169	4.72016431	0.004366
Ier5	0.784115826	1.36650504	4.71990044	0.0043671
Gm42815	-0.817079571	-1.8915489	-4.7187135	0.004372
Evi2a	1.585965996	-0.5153169	4.71695765	0.0043793
Serpina1b	1.856195947	-1.7200108	4.70963006	0.0044097
Kcnk6	0.778411865	1.49165786	4.69111598	0.0044878
Arhgdib	2.027771323	1.82985925	4.69085033	0.0044889
Lck	1.330667421	0.15168539	4.68909645	0.0044964
Naaa	1.665733625	1.52253282	4.67274035	0.0045668
Glipr1	2.229867815	-0.2104814	4.6656154	0.0045979

Cd83	1.658583333	1.00365143	4.6620796	0.0046134
Plekho2	0.987635599	2.71009697	4.65799052	0.0046314
5031425F14Rik	2.284252268	-3.9183829	4.65699139	0.0046358
Lbh	0.974796712	2.48427567	4.65301106	0.0046535
Bcl3	2.07629598	-0.2743118	4.641724	0.0047039
Slc1a4	-1.42570161	1.80806449	-4.6358652	0.0047303
Trim34a	0.689166444	-0.3680621	4.62798499	0.0047661
P2ry6	0.912905359	2.39480695	4.62143793	0.0047961
Gbp7	3.009319291	0.20469597	4.62060814	0.0047999
Cd84	2.535638555	-0.7958503	4.60289471	0.0048822
Ptprv	2.386606045	-3.026078	4.59280179	0.0049298
Sdc3	1.141071139	2.93242686	4.58505956	0.0049667
Gm37034	-1.602867969	-4.477661	-4.5777519	0.0050018
Gm7582	2.047367633	-0.7096128	4.57177393	0.0050307
Adrb1	2.815356974	-1.5378784	4.56859202	0.0050462
Slamf9	1.884637421	1.83285954	4.55642691	0.0051059
Slc28a2	1.827935771	-2.0858653	4.5358014	0.0052089
RP23-325D10.4	0.911660852	-2.9828035	4.53280062	0.0052241
Rab8b	0.650334029	2.52895103	4.53227953	0.0052268
Padi2	1.997394623	-1.1857078	4.51793045	0.0053001
Gatm	1.446579592	2.14576188	4.50894171	0.0053467
Ddit4	-0.812776249	6.15167272	-4.4904859	0.0054438
Tap2	0.674561591	3.19156947	4.48704963	0.0054621
Lhfp13	1.176736607	-4.2180389	4.48125389	0.0054931
5031414D18Rik	1.787302171	-1.5994074	4.47534775	0.005525
Zeb2os	1.806445331	-1.6253111	4.4634996	0.0055895
Mndal	2.260986996	-0.1350481	4.4613623	0.0056012
Trpm2	3.964504689	-3.5641249	4.4603237	0.0056069
Arhgap27os3	3.532508877	-2.7378627	4.4561326	0.00563
Parvg	2.461094856	-1.3436661	4.45514779	0.0056354
Fam65b	2.487921633	-2.7501331	4.45001065	0.0056639
Neurl3	1.479836949	0.82363586	4.44926042	0.0056681
Adam10	-0.640716554	4.37405208	-4.4462813	0.0056847
Clec9a	4.119338874	-2.1169404	4.44627614	0.0056848
Gm42829	-0.848836763	-1.9356055	-4.4460287	0.0056861
Klrk1	2.505377995	-3.8711411	4.4417771	0.0057099
Tlr2	1.31510089	0.56661772	4.43456426	0.0057506
Adat3	-0.854528728	1.00475588	-4.4300986	0.005776
H2-D1	1.023176734	7.81099652	4.42726691	0.0057921
Lsp1	0.900108596	1.47113891	4.42259163	0.0058188
Gbp3	3.467701115	-0.7051567	4.41689428	0.0058516
Kcnab2	2.0694382	-1.510163	4.40834561	0.0059012
Kif24	1.254230075	-3.1657457	4.40658259	0.0059115
Nlrp1a	2.530071254	-3.1364516	4.39934408	0.005954
Lcp1	0.658490439	3.24789847	4.39933784	0.005954
Crmp1	1.676600646	-2.7020627	4.38646693	0.0060304

Dock11	0.869602651	-0.3001735	4.38380355	0.0060463
Nlrc4	2.177131909	-1.5914362	4.37860789	0.0060776
Chst3	1.811171643	-2.7825353	4.37133605	0.0061216
Rab7b	1.046258891	-0.1737598	4.36420597	0.0061652
Zbp1	5.07032309	-1.8672286	4.36327003	0.0061709
Gmfg	0.758215505	0.81841899	4.36321142	0.0061713
Cxcl16	1.398221341	1.55631051	4.36016632	0.00619
E030037K01Rik	-1.591101031	-2.5350363	-4.3591516	0.0061962
1810011H11Rik	1.683086476	-1.5777173	4.35581222	0.0062169
Ighg2b	7.011460151	1.01871587	4.35281806	0.0062354
Il12rb2	2.319233927	-4.2825961	4.34732422	0.0062696
A530099J19Rik	3.56225482	-2.6249869	4.34500159	0.0062842
Icam1	1.288229612	2.32631035	4.34082574	0.0063104
Gm37447	-0.724890197	-1.7785413	-4.3405945	0.0063119
Dock2	2.569123364	-0.5202562	4.32869728	0.0063873
Cd37	2.50379075	-0.7796554	4.31541525	0.0064727
Tlr12	3.244533616	-3.2159149	4.31457408	0.0064782
Fbxo16	0.617800957	2.33772011	4.29132157	0.0066311
H2-T24	1.069272469	-0.0953965	4.28951888	0.0066431
Slc22a15	0.882868669	-3.1014211	4.2820221	0.0066934
Serpina3n	1.475825156	2.90657193	4.27947815	0.0067105
Gm43603	-1.659059187	-2.1295252	-4.2677314	0.0067904
Prokr2	-1.638285154	-4.2135845	-4.2673818	0.0067928
Adam19	1.373500648	0.59815444	4.26632285	0.0068
Card9	1.842623343	-1.1101345	4.2637315	0.0068178
Uba7	0.97884696	0.90980369	4.25960735	0.0068463
Gngt2	1.89880074	-1.446079	4.25941535	0.0068476
Susd3	1.929347395	-2.0229108	4.25898713	0.0068506
Cerk	0.747695566	0.56406751	4.24519217	0.0069467
Csprs	1.935751677	-1.2149006	4.24330188	0.00696
Tfap2e	-1.872169734	-3.7492461	-4.2398669	0.0069843
Zmynd15	2.0725974	-1.9722658	4.23818238	0.0069962
Cmah	2.318622531	-0.790803	4.23622255	0.0070101
Slfn2	2.355290368	2.27892532	4.22261061	0.0071075
Irf4	2.75761589	-0.4829358	4.2213592	0.0071165
Lipg	2.315536729	-0.7425115	4.21595528	0.0071557
Pnpla7	0.629736607	0.13777879	4.21334034	0.0071747
F730043M19Rik	2.364778409	-2.6376527	4.20898232	0.0072066
Lyn	1.179704092	1.83096098	4.20878128	0.007208
Hook1	-0.933015071	2.87371897	-4.2087364	0.0072084
Siglecg	4.070254284	-4.0047448	4.20854941	0.0072097
Lacc1	1.573315368	-0.3050557	4.20729145	0.007219
BC021785	-1.747621798	-5.4110699	-4.2001707	0.0072715
Faxc	1.43388123	-1.4978746	4.19918771	0.0072788
Fam49b	0.716882354	2.3060718	4.19660174	0.0072979
Tifa	1.286427044	-0.9199923	4.19566172	0.0073049

Cfp	1.506664776	2.50284525	4.19326629	0.0073228
Plxnc1	2.092081955	-1.4182578	4.19254114	0.0073282
Rabgef1	-0.607328119	2.46339809	-4.1796764	0.007425
Jade1	-0.611041117	1.08084557	-4.1744728	0.0074646
Fcrls	1.828869999	1.21766595	4.17136449	0.0074883
Rep15	1.626065188	-2.9110568	4.17095839	0.0074914
Cd5	3.81163428	-2.411236	4.16334164	0.00755
Igf2bp3	2.459574223	-5.4366132	4.15396339	0.0076229
Phf11b	4.095837002	-0.5515524	4.14773559	0.0076718
Siglec1	2.559456571	0.0379471	4.14049848	0.0077289
Rassf2	1.177340247	0.62937098	4.13937686	0.0077379
Shank1	1.087454618	-3.4039583	4.13925436	0.0077388
Trim10	1.504101472	-2.8775824	4.13911538	0.0077399
Mup-ps25	-1.162409066	-3.246091	-4.1296383	0.0078157
Igha	7.087978427	1.4138576	4.11852945	0.0079056
Slc37a2	0.616350627	-0.3865244	4.11524266	0.0079324
RP23-181P23.4	-1.293389534	-4.3155054	-4.1117386	0.0079611
Rgs10	1.423701384	0.8363824	4.10862485	0.0079867
Lilra5	0.954083293	-0.6528796	4.10033389	0.0080554
1700066B19Rik	1.301601762	-3.6140868	4.09753028	0.0080787
Tnfrsf4	1.473111239	-1.1076805	4.0943344	0.0081054
Milr1	2.599888184	-2.9924911	4.07540248	0.0082659
Socs3	1.675835864	0.41893788	4.07184857	0.0082964
Aif1	3.308495314	-0.9864418	4.07161851	0.0082984
Rnase6	3.150588471	-0.4090558	4.0708227	0.0083052
Gm7120	0.635982867	-0.6127042	4.06354502	0.0083682
Gm10499	1.251095311	-2.5724333	4.0627322	0.0083752
Spsb1	0.680447142	-0.6063799	4.06131208	0.0083876
H2-M3	1.239612735	2.08880525	4.04927197	0.0084932
Slfm5	1.240159839	1.66634483	4.03112557	0.0086553
Ripk3	2.619909685	-1.3208242	4.02789263	0.0086846
Lgmn	1.008434814	3.71217952	4.02514486	0.0087095
Gimap6	0.981654991	0.44109694	4.02492286	0.0087116
Ccdc27	1.894453554	-4.1073279	4.0246625	0.0087139
Trim12c	0.739899878	0.2944725	4.01713414	0.0087827
Csf2rb2	1.524009735	0.08362574	4.01616357	0.0087916
P2ry14	3.345923114	-5.0999454	4.01232352	0.008827
Erc61	2.127649972	-2.8699543	4.00744636	0.0088722
Lgals3	1.364244591	1.61810598	4.00329667	0.0089108
Hpse	1.09781847	0.17861793	3.99516913	0.008987
Clec10a	1.678859655	0.56385154	3.99061695	0.0090301
Sh2d5	1.38923592	-4.2374188	3.98995102	0.0090364
Cmpk2	1.252088244	1.20100698	3.98555396	0.0090782
Figl1	3.22661792	-4.0319079	3.98421876	0.0090909
Dusp2	3.775639137	-2.1554406	3.97648611	0.0091651
Scimp	2.196706959	-1.8918873	3.97630751	0.0091668

Slamf7	4.277627862	-2.3201603	3.97322177	0.0091966
Rab3il1	0.740362023	-0.0119728	3.97223572	0.0092062
Prdm1	1.185393731	-0.7170489	3.9703242	0.0092247
Dapp1	0.883319104	-0.9272356	3.97027595	0.0092252
Gm5580	-0.918405759	-1.3604325	-3.9616651	0.0093092
Adgre5	0.969184362	1.9855351	3.95997086	0.0093258
Casp1	2.169607018	0.22117915	3.95650233	0.00936
Nlrc3	1.949256423	-4.090643	3.94421253	0.0094822
Gbp9	1.59611077	-0.252319	3.94025397	0.0095219
Sema4d	0.951551936	1.55162712	3.93257559	0.0095996
Marcksl1	0.875691178	2.82496325	3.92240548	0.0097035
Lat	2.549668252	-2.8757724	3.91502269	0.0097797
Parp12	0.775540933	2.46239159	3.90976483	0.0098345
Kif4	2.910389082	-3.2787861	3.90894921	0.009843
Htra2	0.700649096	0.28080305	3.9087396	0.0098452
Sacs	0.819949042	-2.3522331	3.90403891	0.0098944
Trib3	-1.031026404	2.55103691	-3.9001936	0.009935
Rasa3	0.849626051	1.48149913	3.89905427	0.009947
Gm7173	0.888020327	-5.9149472	3.89825131	0.0099555
Zap70	4.040435593	-2.6484883	3.89123276	0.0100301
Racgap1	2.489112406	-2.6165623	3.88890969	0.010055
Nlrp1b	2.732802264	-4.7228383	3.87404217	0.0102156
Cd33	0.83958047	-1.219534	3.87360941	0.0102203
D6ErtD527e	1.580227957	-5.1891034	3.86588218	0.010305
Amz1	1.364756899	-2.5531579	3.86494564	0.0103153
Gm7030	0.795627885	0.3612908	3.86207701	0.0103469
Gcsam	3.15467024	-3.3396661	3.86057495	0.0103636
Ccl9	1.825311978	2.05498057	3.84076106	0.0105858
Ankrd44	0.924652102	-0.7698208	3.8399394	0.0105951
Nrros	1.182920889	-0.4084738	3.8341352	0.0106613
Gm6225	1.139769498	-2.7969961	3.82218113	0.010799
4632428N05Rik	1.589544439	1.19303874	3.82139516	0.0108082
Fscn1	1.179262679	0.30112687	3.81536785	0.0108785
Insl3	1.227633659	-2.3616826	3.81215511	0.0109161
Inpp4b	1.536121166	-2.9215062	3.8060826	0.0109878
Plekhd1os	-1.201738484	-0.0057589	-3.7989121	0.011073
Batf	2.616667568	-0.7858401	3.79870515	0.0110755
Gpr173	0.823920445	-2.1799025	3.7967259	0.0110992
Unc13d	2.652259655	-2.2274922	3.78717024	0.0112143
Trim2	-0.638319718	2.14911794	-3.7863411	0.0112243
Xaf1	1.713422982	0.27632155	3.78426314	0.0112496
Clec5a	1.333020005	-2.7760035	3.78249525	0.0112711
Dck	0.941580169	0.41602098	3.77655904	0.0113437
Ap1s2	1.082382976	-0.195939	3.77617219	0.0113484
Prkcb	0.994323889	-0.1834401	3.77586936	0.0113522
Gda	1.630311526	1.0002583	3.77199907	0.0113998

Gm16712	-0.710430843	-2.3794584	-3.7716539	0.0114041
Gpr68	1.903562483	-2.8979896	3.77075533	0.0114152
Gm37131	0.874817698	0.46848285	3.76934971	0.0114326
Arsi	1.587736522	-1.6751671	3.76854146	0.0114426
AA465934	1.047494131	-2.2994901	3.75875537	0.0115646
Gpr176	3.36947606	-3.6032557	3.7549734	0.0116122
Gm21975	3.819532846	-3.4627351	3.75350746	0.0116307
Sirpa	1.931363597	1.48803904	3.74827675	0.0116969
Mybl1	1.083019948	-2.124383	3.74661845	0.011718
Rsad2	2.680310513	-0.801022	3.74520035	0.0117361
Cd300ld	2.022206285	-1.9368156	3.7301528	0.0119298
Nxpe5	2.102296342	-2.4664515	3.72864761	0.0119494
Gm12319	1.635185978	-1.3545983	3.72673321	0.0119743
Gm14321	1.792886298	-1.8751135	3.71782958	0.0120912
Bhlhe40	1.262661684	1.04135589	3.71408887	0.0121406
Gm11127	1.911707149	0.88427787	3.71398529	0.012142
Galnt5	-0.786303464	-1.1339956	-3.7117042	0.0121723
Gm26722	1.332701748	-2.0903925	3.70932255	0.012204
Rasa4	0.863451572	0.29844	3.70540374	0.0122564
Abcg3	3.141710822	-3.3549796	3.70489129	0.0122632
Gm28417	1.5176982	-2.8756436	3.69757453	0.0123618
Orc1	1.246967675	-4.3125657	3.68710381	0.0125043
Klra9	2.626215681	-2.4709544	3.68177991	0.0125775
Sp100	1.780394082	-0.1643483	3.68043156	0.0125961
Cdca2	1.768029748	-2.7713581	3.6753021	0.0126672
Vis1	2.278465024	-0.2043319	3.67221872	0.0127102
Slc10a6	1.479075475	-0.5497681	3.6673578	0.0127783
Ifi202b	2.03563426	0.8134433	3.66313209	0.0128378
Tnfaip8	1.12433474	-0.9944925	3.6627069	0.0128438
Usp18	2.175257091	0.40749408	3.66074766	0.0128715
Clcf1	1.054279657	-1.6126034	3.65265235	0.0129867
Nr1d2	0.590122702	3.53441992	3.65222492	0.0129928
Gm28053	1.829987161	-2.6050699	3.65057697	0.0130164
I830077J02Rik	2.505106437	-3.0249657	3.64688932	0.0130694
Il3ra	1.350449243	0.61694772	3.62353577	0.0134107
Gnmt	-0.775395001	4.25507666	-3.6094244	0.0136219
Trim5	0.791640239	-0.3184612	3.60247187	0.0137273
Fgr	3.768895374	-2.2348785	3.6010083	0.0137496
Lilra6	2.403534416	-3.0342794	3.59278452	0.0138757
H2-K1	2.122098082	2.44082492	3.59255126	0.0138792
Ccr6	2.522518608	-2.5550493	3.58732506	0.0139601
Kmo	2.297681836	-3.5492969	3.57970662	0.0140789
Parp9	0.750272824	3.13923432	3.57187203	0.0142022
Rtn4r	1.881031233	-1.282084	3.56810367	0.014262
Efnb3	-0.818466416	-1.5744539	-3.563927	0.0143285
Bgn	0.587941088	4.09334021	3.56310027	0.0143417

Rtp4	2.997323012	1.28730937	3.56060475	0.0143817
Ighj4	2.863408281	1.31752544	3.55751173	0.0144314
Plaur	0.679038154	-1.5981072	3.55722615	0.014436
Gm13523	1.227428258	-1.4809482	3.5569553	0.0144404
Il22ra1	-1.006687414	-2.3019184	-3.5566034	0.0144461
Chad	-1.053529338	1.21431361	-3.5540918	0.0144866
Zfp69	-1.119974325	-2.2321374	-3.5475703	0.0145926
Bub1b	2.800333717	-2.2485343	3.54734698	0.0145962
Arhgef2	0.916325224	-0.2615758	3.54168634	0.0146889
Il1b	2.488195753	-1.8858815	3.53988027	0.0147186
Foxd2os	0.655188394	-1.8282288	3.53396367	0.0148164
Naip2	2.238335547	-1.1609379	3.53152904	0.0148569
Ccdc109b	2.636698484	-1.2752921	3.52789494	0.0149175
Dpep2	1.245968724	-3.2007927	3.52676892	0.0149363
Asz1	1.422273393	-4.1625924	3.52210051	0.0150147
Nfkbie	1.191324992	0.70774516	3.52186876	0.0150186
Crlf3	0.765828353	0.65826764	3.50852424	0.0152454
H2-K2	2.418533351	0.10576195	3.50351388	0.0153315
Abcg1	1.083740331	0.413325	3.50260309	0.0153472
Gm20488	-1.581664386	-3.0843827	-3.5004556	0.0153843
Ddx58	1.099314818	0.55853886	3.49592088	0.015463
Cenpa	2.315292335	-2.5246876	3.4947392	0.0154836
Gm13625	1.718997879	-1.8782129	3.49374053	0.0155011
Hnrnpa3	0.586784617	2.10527066	3.49336379	0.0155076
Lppr4	1.560814004	-5.2400296	3.49074518	0.0155534
Hrh2	0.917157299	-0.9361892	3.49064909	0.0155551
Irf1	0.638488227	1.99484408	3.48711478	0.0156172
Rxfp1	1.068631895	-1.37511	3.48472238	0.0156594
Gm15697	1.642735603	-4.1789358	3.48236196	0.0157011
Ahcy	1.24244913	-2.7544356	3.48047259	0.0157346
Tnfsf9	1.904646415	-1.7019607	3.47751574	0.0157872
Cxcr4	1.780757748	0.08638743	3.47705915	0.0157954
Gdpd2	1.641645191	-2.8929331	3.47548826	0.0158234
Gm37200	-0.775797817	-1.5786542	-3.4671106	0.015974
Gm18953	0.656619962	1.35055143	3.46566938	0.0159999
Cit	1.440109202	-4.1393183	3.46470367	0.0160174
Trim59	1.605837688	-1.0547821	3.46009206	0.0161012
AF251705	1.508597827	1.03795053	3.45258974	0.0162385
Nsl1	1.149946861	-2.8201052	3.44730257	0.0163361
Ptger2	2.983965631	-2.9907303	3.4460429	0.0163594
Tnfaip3	1.30181741	-0.7858479	3.4382085	0.0165054
Mthfd2	-0.95583072	4.14454544	-3.4381522	0.0165065
Trem2	1.539812233	-1.1149141	3.43729437	0.0165226
Slc7a7	1.225436082	-0.1832232	3.42403222	0.0167734
Cd4	4.397224938	-1.8647545	3.42057318	0.0168395
Xdh	1.376826799	2.36604258	3.41281956	0.0169888

Serpinb6c	-1.821604347	-3.174301	-3.4122757	0.0169994
Fam107a	1.364079265	-0.7590607	3.4041408	0.0171577
Itgae	5.244658083	-2.2220533	3.40312594	0.0171776
Klra8	3.563663936	-1.1767055	3.39570366	0.0173236
Gm26682	1.334716745	-3.780527	3.39356798	0.0173659
RP24-317F6.7	-1.43903944	-1.5549435	-3.3931372	0.0173745
Nedd9	1.339015747	0.54597712	3.38805857	0.0174756
Nusap1	2.961308952	-2.7053352	3.38787261	0.0174793
Npl	1.599497095	0.0474519	3.38753563	0.017486
Timeless	0.844241495	-2.2080221	3.38601853	0.0175164
Tgfb1	1.221383773	0.99004035	3.38570021	0.0175228
Gna15	1.053602449	-1.3861484	3.38381837	0.0175605
Tuba8	0.740317256	-0.973782	3.38365516	0.0175638
Ccl12	2.486367009	-0.2111757	3.38259405	0.0175851
Tgfb1	1.318590432	3.31211808	3.38201537	0.0175967
Gm28036	-1.258557594	0.11213032	-3.3783728	0.0176702
BC055324	0.687687812	-1.7234343	3.37346808	0.0177697
Ppp1r18os	1.523811328	-2.350051	3.37272462	0.0177849
Dtx3l	1.04394793	2.51975987	3.36784705	0.0178845
Galnt7	0.830319001	0.04075857	3.36401346	0.0179633
Trp53i11	1.395182177	-0.7198105	3.36084892	0.0180286
5930420M18Rik	0.756649358	-0.3998921	3.35550448	0.0181395
Phf11d	1.835092045	-1.306002	3.35461918	0.0181579
Trim63	-1.67349137	-3.0380953	-3.3534092	0.0181832
Ticam2	1.684667587	-1.2468454	3.34782788	0.0183001
Tsc22d3	1.091343044	2.72718891	3.34751076	0.0183068
Limd2	0.79349083	1.44597133	3.34518856	0.0183557
Galnt12	2.807304138	-1.9846717	3.34484827	0.0183629
2810417H13Rik	2.990978149	-3.2720305	3.34032897	0.0184586
Itgax	4.367423148	-1.6719424	3.33785969	0.0185111
Casp4	1.076604886	-0.6600105	3.33702153	0.018529
Matk	2.197892666	-3.4225839	3.33690524	0.0185315
Gpm6b	0.935537202	0.49673712	3.33588734	0.0185532
Rab39	1.86655281	-3.026425	3.33555056	0.0185604
Ccl6	1.807410132	3.20052057	3.3239675	0.0188097
Egr2	1.326745329	-2.3242015	3.31799581	0.0189397
Zfp941	0.956495694	-3.1621431	3.31792694	0.0189412
Gm37621	1.085816091	-3.5826367	3.31441127	0.0190182
Sh3bp1	1.419796888	0.49447913	3.30976265	0.0191206
Ppp1r26	-2.097737889	-1.8606148	-3.3095493	0.0191253
Rnd1	-0.895493544	0.7509179	-3.306966	0.0191825
Zfand4	0.974965757	-0.4657857	3.30383703	0.019252
Bbs12	0.655111264	-0.3342628	3.30258025	0.0192799
Gm37969	0.657263974	-2.7222454	3.30252609	0.0192812
Mrc1	1.325927514	2.36838345	3.29853814	0.0193703
Rtn4rl2	1.347655181	-2.6014494	3.29839712	0.0193734

Rrad	1.229767953	-0.4886203	3.29729628	0.0193981
Sntg1	1.880856586	-7.2481008	3.2953963	0.0194408
Pilrb2	1.746346768	-3.1529367	3.2924738	0.0195067
Aff2	0.717969638	-2.2944725	3.28971068	0.0195692
Pla2g2d	1.955737545	-1.333019	3.28674529	0.0196366
Tub	0.800856689	-0.5827246	3.28416856	0.0196953
Ccl7	2.152251354	0.09004678	3.28307698	0.0197202
1700056E22Rik	-0.764236544	-0.6633125	-3.2818551	0.0197482
Muc13	0.793938912	-1.3656432	3.27858304	0.0198233
H2-Ob	3.710761286	-2.7010198	3.27740246	0.0198505
Dnajb3	1.837616988	-2.4210966	3.27326011	0.0199461
Rap2b	0.660005911	0.54108461	3.27242287	0.0199655
Slc7a11	-1.583633698	-0.3054012	-3.2718318	0.0199792
Gm12500	1.278113812	-3.605183	3.27119357	0.019994
Stx11	1.74968394	-1.1058376	3.27094639	0.0199998
Al467606	1.194854227	-0.182494	3.27055288	0.0200089
Rasgrp3	1.413582122	-0.3391064	3.26848755	0.020057
Etv5	1.110511832	-0.0986441	3.26546501	0.0201275
Casc5	2.647743549	-4.9981969	3.26313129	0.0201822
Tmem168	0.849587079	1.90803467	3.26044776	0.0202453
Cyb5r2	-1.284619267	-3.6490757	-3.2602304	0.0202504
Stab1	1.131414731	1.40197641	3.25879913	0.0202841
C1qtnf1	0.767999057	1.54581831	3.25630483	0.0203431
Rrm2	0.936482755	0.77972673	3.25394718	0.0203989
Clec2i	2.103994588	-3.927923	3.24976407	0.0204985
Nek6	1.478002675	-1.764295	3.24645196	0.0205778
Srms	1.981855035	-3.5836973	3.24369347	0.020644
Snx22	2.091464662	-1.568125	3.24322583	0.0206553
Pcdhgb4	-1.698084267	-2.9469239	-3.2428077	0.0206653
Ptafr	1.220813174	1.01052496	3.23724493	0.0207998
Apoe	1.217745828	4.62837152	3.23248153	0.0209158
Tacc3	1.009664448	-0.9137601	3.22659496	0.02106
Gabrb1	1.557363849	-5.2897536	3.22329159	0.0211415
Brip1	1.367140402	-2.9685284	3.22175575	0.0211794
Zfp36l1-ps	1.635128853	-2.4920847	3.21915733	0.0212439
Ckap2	2.123670424	-0.9914439	3.21541987	0.021337
Ifi205	1.832487725	-0.8374334	3.21482083	0.0213519
Sh3bp2	0.877031548	0.40195576	3.20992583	0.0214746
Hmox1	0.752756714	1.81922394	3.20815164	0.0215192
Oasl2	2.664436314	-0.0769542	3.20481813	0.0216034
Kcnd1	1.025725978	-1.7434084	3.20449937	0.0216115
A930012L18Rik	-1.242643179	-3.5762954	-3.204284	0.021617
4930590J08Rik	-0.723989665	-3.9082995	-3.2036959	0.0216319
Wnt6	0.935571826	0.11244668	3.19749579	0.0217896
Extl1	-0.789132655	2.41286224	-3.1848123	0.0221164
4931440P22Rik	0.81613865	-3.5520901	3.18163132	0.0221993

Fbxw10	2.177325394	-4.0749782	3.18107302	0.0222138
Mbd4	0.703063764	-1.2500088	3.17998789	0.0222422
Cep55	1.767090611	-1.8155925	3.1741945	0.0223942
Ms4a14	1.5426008	-3.8532688	3.17313451	0.0224222
Cmklr1	0.914844879	1.23011829	3.17205242	0.0224507
Ube2l6	1.326428452	0.89742705	3.17046004	0.0224928
Trpv2	1.241460264	0.39029927	3.1687941	0.022537
Pcdhga3	-2.358693957	-3.684895	-3.1621458	0.0227141
Fyn	1.197294176	0.36300229	3.16112213	0.0227415
Baz1a	0.706992435	0.31129452	3.15896346	0.0227995
Slc25a18	1.8260664	-3.3460104	3.15716989	0.0228477
Stk10	1.028486106	1.00018688	3.15527095	0.022899
Arhgap11a	1.556974737	-1.9854745	3.15375967	0.0229398
Tnfsf10	1.762166504	-0.0461165	3.15279837	0.0229658
Socs1	1.129658443	0.67358373	3.15210571	0.0229846
Gmip	0.676479212	0.66600085	3.14928351	0.0230613
Elf4	1.331495831	-0.2733965	3.13782096	0.0233756
Mcm5	1.85883406	-0.2043233	3.13354542	0.0234941
Mmp12	1.407367724	-2.9597724	3.13342684	0.0234974
Cdca8	2.060247485	-2.2485224	3.12034272	0.0238641
Bst1	1.672751913	-1.8217952	3.11384608	0.0240486
Dnah2	2.473297545	-6.0608715	3.11018115	0.0241533
Prcp	1.079770829	1.89764085	3.10478805	0.0243084
Cfb	2.402450113	1.88864239	3.10431043	0.0243222
Cpne1	0.860631777	0.62022229	3.10403767	0.0243301
Al506816	0.844361147	-2.0791369	3.10399402	0.0243313
Trim30d	2.180057071	-1.4669204	3.10304767	0.0243587
Rin3	0.893963592	-0.2174141	3.10073543	0.0244257
Gimap8	1.832891964	-1.1704121	3.09522144	0.0245862
Rad54l	2.083139959	-3.4679875	3.09514534	0.0245884
Pcdhb4	1.170670628	-3.9980759	3.0907696	0.0247167
Catsperg1	0.690737076	-2.4826545	3.08873703	0.0247765
Agpat4	0.960933174	0.00591953	3.08816374	0.0247934
Ly6c2	1.489806078	-0.8013335	3.08637647	0.0248462
Psmb10	0.909895323	3.34989464	3.08590047	0.0248603
A630033H20Rik	2.635132568	-4.5279211	3.08579603	0.0248634
Stk17b	0.590711288	3.63742681	3.08539795	0.0248751
Pik3cg	1.22293649	-0.4298494	3.08400806	0.0249163
Gm4477	0.927288708	-2.9184192	3.08119288	0.025
Atoh8	-0.840196288	2.59847109	-3.0762444	0.0251478
Pltp	1.081828696	3.49714971	3.07316184	0.0252403
Naip6	1.816788045	-2.5629696	3.07258734	0.0252576
Tmem246	-0.602491102	1.9856412	-3.0717698	0.0252822
Gm4262	-0.922967875	-2.9589449	-3.0704246	0.0253228
Ipcef1	3.632918211	-3.5335103	3.05983145	0.0256449
Lpcat1	1.065292446	0.69869053	3.05930128	0.0256612

C5ar2	2.914605569	-2.6046178	3.05857874	0.0256833
Nfatc2	0.722750487	-0.3884452	3.05778799	0.0257076
Gm13219	-1.431701267	-3.8430643	-3.0546529	0.025804
Fas	0.615865842	3.32636532	3.04931053	0.0259693
6330416G13Rik	1.789921593	-1.6243957	3.04819381	0.026004
Spp1	3.025596355	-3.194259	3.04755481	0.0260239
Tmem151b	1.713774054	-3.6151091	3.04683843	0.0260462
Slc12a5	1.452788476	-2.6849245	3.043779	0.0261417
Pram1	2.032620271	-4.2582085	3.04142905	0.0262153
Ctsz	0.639046507	5.40241156	3.03702982	0.0263538
Tnfaip2	1.351409104	-1.4874228	3.03462645	0.0264297
Dok2	1.261905533	0.02610296	3.02980952	0.0265827
Myo7a	1.105310337	-2.3743202	3.02701957	0.0266718
Fam167b	0.975222272	-0.2384267	3.02576767	0.0267119
Akap5	1.062289529	-4.6612745	3.02318196	0.0267948
Bcat1	3.112267313	-3.5475697	3.01898355	0.0269302
Plekha2	0.714025381	1.2558451	3.00968101	0.0272327
Tnfaip8l1	1.021927956	-1.6233673	3.00751646	0.0273037
Ifi204	1.697610027	0.00945065	3.0050947	0.0273833
Msc	1.410643095	-2.7574624	3.00362703	0.0274316
B230322F03Rik	0.781342577	-0.8505792	3.00254431	0.0274674
Prg4	-1.558676899	-3.5945262	-3.0011459	0.0275136
Ncapg	2.662944001	-4.2581336	2.99724738	0.027643
Sass6	0.778919584	-1.7311881	2.99322108	0.0277773
Dgke	-0.687970177	-0.7083562	-2.98968	0.027896
Myo5a	0.799563478	0.0527405	2.98661778	0.0279992
Rasgrp4	1.070417286	-2.704667	2.98572642	0.0280293
Alox5ap	2.636609075	1.82217224	2.9822935	0.0281455
Gm11948	0.642526135	-0.4526319	2.97965794	0.0282351
Spon1	1.252596553	0.30438415	2.9785408	0.0282732
Gm42611	1.083203397	-4.0233829	2.97495586	0.0283958
Gm11365	-1.216926411	0.07589175	-2.974234	0.0284205
A130010J15Rik	-1.037935058	0.89228849	-2.9718537	0.0285023
Gm18342	0.805743866	-0.0081521	2.96584889	0.0287098
Nras	1.131933525	1.23186226	2.96525314	0.0287305
Gm12057	-3.419487999	-0.4217578	-2.9612902	0.0288684
Mx2	2.302049108	-1.7489063	2.96125025	0.0288698
Mterf2	0.887273466	-0.2545525	2.95977843	0.0289212
Hmmr	2.191264252	-2.4760964	2.95288926	0.0291633
Il13ra2	1.891944356	-1.1838107	2.95164684	0.0292072
Ptpre	1.205470646	-0.260689	2.94833645	0.0293245
Cpne2	0.819557218	-0.0609643	2.94665558	0.0293842
4930570G19Rik	1.755767571	-4.2579082	2.94176196	0.029559
Zeb1	0.680966616	0.37017552	2.94073734	0.0295957
Ehd3	1.07877852	0.19466518	2.94048228	0.0296048
Scpep1	0.6734273	3.59320614	2.94039992	0.0296078

Gm38372	-0.682221254	-1.9180676	-2.9394541	0.0296418
B430306N03Rik	2.032365502	-2.7764255	2.93446341	0.0298217
Gm42577	0.699072875	-3.0731345	2.93387325	0.0298431
Gm28539	1.160174138	-0.4838766	2.93130485	0.0299362
RP24-441P8.3	-0.982419435	-2.1957837	-2.9312992	0.0299364
Gimap5	1.825117738	-2.244699	2.92477418	0.0301745
Fbxo48	2.375850259	-4.4883879	2.92283736	0.0302456
Gpr34	0.885800853	-1.3273894	2.92240814	0.0302613
Kbtbd11	1.377182496	-0.6814822	2.91883167	0.0303931
Nudt16	0.847210713	-1.1160532	2.91629228	0.0304871
Slc41a3	0.659390795	-0.2689078	2.91587674	0.0305025
Gm17193	1.212659197	-0.5912954	2.91328916	0.0305986
Anxa13	-0.731082072	5.55879141	-2.9128867	0.0306136
Tmem86a	0.673640694	1.79463575	2.90932702	0.0307465
Gm13421	0.808493188	-0.2626503	2.90852564	0.0307765
1700010I14Rik	1.78163321	-3.3699114	2.90830453	0.0307848
Gm9917	0.72611108	-3.289827	2.90658073	0.0308494
Plk1	1.829907686	-1.5010975	2.90489577	0.0309128
Pou2f2	2.183731738	-2.8420838	2.90161075	0.0310367
Psd2	1.190493352	-4.9506234	2.90087507	0.0310645
Gm16793	0.749834666	-2.9143852	2.90084382	0.0310657
Gpr157	1.070518362	-0.3979534	2.89622676	0.0312409
Dhx58	1.600972018	-0.2639065	2.89425956	0.0313159
Otud7a	-0.912246334	1.16207615	-2.8887776	0.031526
Maf	1.025343948	1.8443697	2.88584025	0.0316392
Il2ra	0.860453662	-1.8413442	2.8851983	0.0316639
RP23-436D14.6	0.838189551	-1.7713732	2.88411003	0.031706
Slc40a1	-0.864161759	-1.4643425	-2.8840879	0.0317069
Kcna3	2.380971618	-2.2643808	2.87961654	0.0318805
Susd1	1.435539169	-0.3083973	2.87659134	0.0319985
Xlr	1.12899966	-2.8731577	2.87648581	0.0320026
A530040E14Rik	1.554991747	-5.1455173	2.87485445	0.0320664
Adap1	1.10709981	-0.2834695	2.87426882	0.0320894
Ltb4r1	1.315136063	-1.3575102	2.87239799	0.0321629
Slc38a2	-0.638880431	4.94931725	-2.8722414	0.032169
Hip1	0.870581521	0.61751256	2.86792584	0.0323392
Gm38077	0.949332391	-0.8403066	2.86630219	0.0324035
Espl1	0.913055517	-1.373992	2.86259586	0.0325507
Fam227a	0.754368203	-0.9836096	2.86097973	0.0326152
Ppapdc3	1.33346535	-1.1151761	2.86076303	0.0326238
4930471C06Rik	1.400052277	-0.5859719	2.85882323	0.0327014
1190002F15Rik	2.089357569	-4.798244	2.85830787	0.032722
Zfp677	0.678456753	-0.7695368	2.85618001	0.0328074
Gm26620	-0.941736622	0.01141264	-2.8533574	0.032921
Prkcq	2.810391779	-2.8338959	2.85282232	0.0329426
RP23-288L22.4	1.806485375	-2.0268484	2.85215201	0.0329697

Apol10b	1.806452319	-3.2163305	2.84993757	0.0330593
Dse	0.973268523	1.16678186	2.8466469	0.0331929
Pdgfb	0.770906797	0.68314512	2.84357467	0.0333182
Gpx2-ps1	-1.626565504	-0.4228396	-2.8415892	0.0333994
Dna2	0.947666676	-1.8538492	2.84127349	0.0334124
Exoc3l2	0.983304527	-0.5428876	2.83947003	0.0334864
Gpr137b	0.885691904	0.07071364	2.83835713	0.0335322
Arl5c	2.550036826	-2.3029039	2.83262243	0.0337691
Samsn1	3.102001641	-2.8833047	2.83060917	0.0338527
Cdt1	0.776680237	0.79560937	2.82855013	0.0339384
1700055D18Rik	1.023639395	-2.6136212	2.82822683	0.0339519
RP23-335G1.1	1.397094521	-2.6477429	2.82707447	0.034
Zscan2	1.158615084	-2.1584153	2.82605032	0.0340429
Spag17	2.380710313	-6.0431318	2.8232766	0.0341591
Ccna2	3.14781666	-2.16222	2.82050973	0.0342755
Fli1	0.832864422	0.37507011	2.82043255	0.0342788
Usp16	-0.796112541	3.68788791	-2.8190528	0.034337
Ywhah	0.694179712	4.33525645	2.81848812	0.0343609
AI504432	3.248526796	-2.2695567	2.81690936	0.0344277
Peg12	1.247099162	-2.6610043	2.8159657	0.0344677
Gabbr2	1.01902063	-3.8170503	2.81377295	0.0345608
Gm2a	1.210965099	3.46333626	2.812456	0.0346169
Chadl	2.647147782	-3.7691336	2.81141927	0.0346611
Gm37691	2.152605157	-3.1712766	2.80919914	0.034756
Hexb	0.590021701	4.97358219	2.80896183	0.0347662
RP23-338G5.3	-0.980966581	-0.4383535	-2.8054027	0.0349189
Syne3	0.836553651	-0.5217361	2.80317317	0.035015
Ankrd33b	1.372822085	-4.0635219	2.80204232	0.0350638
Stard8	0.870055191	1.47469307	2.80150074	0.0350872
5033417F24Rik	0.67082215	-0.5738726	2.8006001	0.0351262
Gm26782	-0.893540581	-1.1153395	-2.7990281	0.0351943
Gm42791	-1.024098815	-3.0923872	-2.7987189	0.0352078
Gng2	1.789603544	0.11248855	2.79749101	0.0352611
Gm20696	-0.781361718	-3.0737831	-2.7966777	0.0352965
Umps	1.359049312	-0.369901	2.79528683	0.0353571
Stap1	3.070127545	-2.2666547	2.7933832	0.0354402
Gm26631	1.926606126	-3.4913477	2.79335209	0.0354416
Cd44	1.881358692	-0.0804543	2.79175608	0.0355115
Dlgap5	3.358214607	-4.1523635	2.79124209	0.035534
Wnt10a	1.46059123	-0.7640068	2.78792046	0.03568
Mov10	0.789194879	0.28605707	2.78588321	0.0357698
Serpine1	1.491445088	-1.4501594	2.78119787	0.0359775
Ccdc88a	0.683499928	-0.3575183	2.78025131	0.0360196
Gm15513	0.634942584	-2.0214017	2.77987476	0.0360363
Gm37902	0.593698398	-0.5717442	2.77972547	0.036043
Spata33	-1.09825353	-0.9323448	-2.7787181	0.0360879

Mob1a	-1.509221654	3.31837182	-2.7761578	0.0362023
Fam217b	1.089263705	-1.5953567	2.77316255	0.0363366
Myb	2.047252883	-3.9517147	2.77038868	0.0364615
Slc2a6	2.141115635	-1.8583408	2.77019315	0.0364703
Gm20449	1.861002499	-3.8972467	2.76712863	0.0366089
A230050P20Rik	0.721892121	0.44423495	2.76643423	0.0366403
Gm17396	0.639740724	-0.7985063	2.76331055	0.0367823
Recql4	2.280370332	-3.553704	2.76238605	0.0368244
Tnfrsf18	1.002357565	-2.2573339	2.75931474	0.0369647
Nrm	1.416465783	-0.6388964	2.75907718	0.0369756
Gm43203	1.385400563	-1.7903526	2.75641914	0.0370976
Ccl28	1.505347341	-3.0830744	2.75640818	0.0370981
S1pr4	2.559405656	-2.193556	2.75433169	0.0371937
Gzmc	-0.979730382	0.18876573	-2.7534646	0.0372337
Agps	0.614446095	1.30074655	2.75240425	0.0372826
Smim17	1.365879985	-4.7320519	2.75196875	0.0373028
8430408G22Rik	1.542604161	0.28230593	2.74971336	0.0374072
Vim	1.115439402	3.26667555	2.74575093	0.0375915
Apol9b	1.602670618	-1.8250255	2.74525633	0.0376146
Tead4	-0.897489594	-1.7131056	-2.7424601	0.0377453
Mki67	3.08257672	-0.719753	2.7423945	0.0377484
Pla2g4b	2.845995707	-3.9358238	2.74195586	0.037769
Rnf213	0.653244981	2.45486484	2.74178269	0.0377771
Aspm	2.955695689	-3.9020589	2.74109533	0.0378093
Rbm12b1	-1.595919212	-2.056674	-2.7395738	0.0378808
Tnfrsf22	0.84934142	-2.2440207	2.73954631	0.0378821
Gm9994	-0.63423963	-4.4764401	-2.7357273	0.0380622
Rgs19	0.871755498	-0.7613726	2.73531704	0.0380816
Sema6d	1.020092253	-1.6544846	2.73080026	0.0382959
Zfp882	0.766305948	-1.2247556	2.72883158	0.0383897
Csf1	0.688430886	1.07973423	2.72873543	0.0383943
Gm4750	1.170800014	-5.1468061	2.72572888	0.0385381
Incenp	0.773658055	1.04597315	2.72485168	0.0385801
Osmr	0.796397525	-0.1506635	2.72478077	0.0385835
Mgl2	1.196475459	0.61664169	2.72413095	0.0386147
Mgp	0.685904775	6.11304859	2.72237013	0.0386994
Gm20492	0.806246834	-0.9204412	2.72178667	0.0387275
Hrh1	1.309079773	-5.5214442	2.71750918	0.0389341
Cmtm3	0.591094406	3.22405076	2.71649878	0.0389831
Tacr1	1.449772491	-4.8016293	2.71476189	0.0390675
RP24-430K15.4	1.389153072	-0.6925431	2.71472701	0.0390692
Adora2a	0.840776952	-1.0816933	2.71443018	0.0390836
9330136K24Rik	0.723639122	-1.9953732	2.71402168	0.0391035
Zfp296	1.99066137	-2.6737322	2.71353711	0.0391271
Gm13139	0.763365097	-3.2535065	2.71333174	0.0391371
Ms4a8a	1.92137573	-0.8267547	2.70861222	0.0393679

Gm13768	0.636883692	1.36934359	2.70838309	0.0393791
Cd93	0.881777804	1.75370784	2.707911	0.0394023
Cacna1h	0.590627345	-0.5747067	2.70641893	0.0394756
Fkbp1b	2.245605846	-0.9763525	2.70376866	0.0396062
Gm2670	1.032679974	-4.962675	2.70022339	0.0397816
Arhgap22	1.063731793	-0.8705295	2.6985426	0.0398651
3110070M22Rik	0.837475346	-0.5301454	2.69500119	0.0400416
Gm20257	1.325355802	0.26809057	2.69225381	0.0401791
D430040D24Rik	0.85500011	-1.0967666	2.69030812	0.0402768
Gm26944	1.027499437	-0.248149	2.68998087	0.0402933
Ccdc50-ps	-0.968358514	-0.0019956	-2.687213	0.0404328
Asf1b	1.448455337	-1.2769837	2.68579561	0.0405044
Mmp19	0.963960306	0.72437461	2.68563777	0.0405124
Pex26	-0.721872759	0.29400017	-2.6820471	0.0406945
Gm26555	1.309352028	-4.7881695	2.67590574	0.0410081
Pilrb1	1.607325924	-3.3617039	2.67385046	0.0411136
Pml	0.621665436	0.44094787	2.67064603	0.0412787
Nrgn	1.103306233	-1.9619928	2.66738064	0.0414478
Tbc1d4	0.652539038	0.3341038	2.66560138	0.0415402
Phyhd1	1.191826584	-0.6706719	2.66554466	0.0415431
Ppm1j	2.679875738	-2.5478454	2.66374401	0.0416369
Gm13091	0.774109664	0.47720103	2.66093459	0.0417836
D930048G16Rik	0.726323153	-2.1491803	2.65997535	0.0418338
Lrrc8c	0.894632008	0.08062257	2.65978291	0.0418439
Lrrk2	1.12574812	-0.8913021	2.65243944	0.0422307
Nt5dc2	0.665142996	0.2404027	2.65201199	0.0422533
Pidd1	0.599805539	-2.7212381	2.64865499	0.0424316
Amd-ps3	-0.671871296	3.63328853	-2.6464235	0.0425505
Gm37062	-0.811792884	-0.9974256	-2.6396677	0.0429127
Irak1bp1	0.801823657	-1.2747311	2.63705354	0.0430538
Cdc25b	1.348578889	0.16642646	2.63677194	0.043069
Hist1h3a	2.0277117	-1.5443348	2.63585207	0.0431188
Ighv1-64	3.843349571	-0.0992086	2.63337085	0.0432534
Ska3	1.650980269	-2.2113357	2.63095504	0.0433848
Fam134c	-0.89968277	2.81969827	-2.6270821	0.0435965
A730056A06Rik	2.284238692	-4.2008604	2.6255927	0.0436782
Cd177	1.12451833	-2.0266036	2.62300639	0.0438205
Gm12216	0.590439856	0.02834274	2.61808902	0.0440923
Itpkb	0.883415947	2.71566987	2.61764606	0.0441169
Herc6	1.038459793	-0.1062855	2.61511017	0.0442579
C030013C21Rik	0.894184437	-2.8801299	2.61329722	0.044359
Hist2h4	-1.46562278	2.44557567	-2.6116891	0.0444489
Nanos1	0.879485814	-3.1992127	2.60962566	0.0445646
Pycard	1.001159358	1.3690435	2.60762292	0.0446771
Slc27a3	0.936319914	-0.050715	2.60261663	0.0449598
2010016I18Rik	3.708880061	-3.1939224	2.59787517	0.0452293

2600006K01Rik	1.421457598	-1.9007056	2.5954566	0.0453674
Nfasc	1.872943612	-3.3894072	2.59147614	0.0455958
Mgat1	0.661040379	-0.1981286	2.59068069	0.0456416
Slc16a3	2.018923404	-2.2420144	2.58924531	0.0457243
Srpk3	1.558779146	-2.8445542	2.58321364	0.0460738
F2r12	2.163831529	-4.5662415	2.58176359	0.0461582
Ppp3cc	0.96180346	0.74180511	2.58153071	0.0461718
Tspan2	0.906453214	1.11425469	2.58139299	0.0461798
H2-T23	0.659094334	1.26555721	2.58047842	0.0462332
Anp32-ps	1.00408061	0.4480899	2.57804675	0.0463755
Sectm1b	1.12630476	-2.3301301	2.57674574	0.0464517
RP23-402P24.5	1.773650555	-2.0234875	2.57559713	0.0465192
Pitpnc1	1.195010731	0.09254452	2.57285408	0.0466808
Zpbp	0.611310786	-4.244046	2.57201704	0.0467302
Spns3	2.557182245	-4.1324261	2.56950759	0.0468787
Fam83d	1.389234709	-2.5491366	2.5678085	0.0469795
Emilin2	0.686685677	1.10246679	2.56745153	0.0470008
Rassf9	-0.613287456	1.72397627	-2.5650015	0.0471466
3110035E14Rik	0.993290566	-1.9771401	2.56373564	0.0472222
Mkl	0.97228172	-0.4848623	2.56172461	0.0473425
Ssh2	1.11307346	0.10085361	2.5615299	0.0473542
Rgag4	1.255844428	-1.0353962	2.5614494	0.047359
2900009J06Rik	-0.960118371	-2.2862428	-2.5605916	0.0474105
Kcnd3	1.466783081	-1.854385	2.55999154	0.0474465
Gcnt1	1.235399914	-1.0010345	2.55917635	0.0474955
Gm11535	-0.778904179	2.93486009	-2.5586061	0.0475298
Pja1	-0.636478998	1.63065979	-2.5585194	0.047535
Irx2	-0.781790324	3.09592156	-2.5525376	0.0478964
Plxnd1	0.946774664	2.01108924	2.55203132	0.0479271
Helz2	0.769967496	0.23661838	2.55062641	0.0480125
Mnda	1.293404467	-0.5699144	2.55058517	0.048015
Rab26os	0.680863412	0.70845723	2.54986199	0.048059
Dclk1	1.244804969	-3.6358447	2.54813921	0.0481641
Fam84b	-0.599742507	4.75493322	-2.5454657	0.0483275
Mcm3	1.376705686	-0.7862875	2.54064861	0.0486236
Gm20547	3.043782351	0.11004664	2.54035093	0.048642
Ren1	-0.864807947	3.53152159	-2.5400222	0.0486623
Amd-ps1	-0.667272539	3.12370442	-2.5380761	0.0487825
Ctsb	0.886449624	5.73301512	2.53455039	0.0490012
Tbc1d1	0.799617913	1.64520438	2.53118007	0.0492113
Il1rl1	1.31771855	-2.8742279	2.52973648	0.0493016
Dusp8	-0.739711599	2.00363637	-2.5256908	0.0495555
Ehbp1l1	0.774358776	2.61124278	2.52003947	0.0499126
Unc5c	2.317992621	-5.6589488	2.51992612	0.0499198
E2f7	2.338384255	-5.2022611	2.51977097	0.0499296

EAP+CCL5 VS. EAP

Rab22a	-1.972989883	1.51185732	-18.078557	4.48E-06
Klra2	1.784409523	-0.8991319	13.8508395	1.86E-05
Gm29253	4.947728353	-4.0666664	11.8295209	4.30E-05
Zfp605	1.255064966	-0.3345057	9.19668822	0.00016
Zfp82	-1.001461075	-2.707722	-8.5704674	0.00023
D830026112Rik	-1.632705357	-3.3019671	-8.4223219	0.0002515
C1d	1.164348644	2.11571707	8.23677455	0.0002818
Ubc	-1.080601164	4.13187355	-7.9518713	0.0003371
Lgals3bp	1.707863954	4.41318646	7.78706663	0.0003748
H2-K2	0.947140596	1.78859893	7.5690749	0.0004326
Il10	2.124099231	-1.6508418	7.34870462	0.0005019
Gm11365	1.371758659	0.15330787	7.23189434	0.0005439
Gna14	0.801804346	0.39201427	7.15856687	0.0005723
H2-Eb1	0.91845972	7.95631757	6.80941621	0.0007339
Gm28053	-1.363565421	-2.371859	-6.754404	0.000764
Fam26f	0.988061623	1.25074636	6.6859674	0.0008034
Gbp10	1.576728445	-0.4956843	6.62777969	0.0008388
Gm26884	2.108210869	-3.5250905	6.62629663	0.0008398
Pigr	1.750677437	2.9645943	6.59950647	0.0008567
Efnb3	0.79174713	-1.5878135	6.59452222	0.0008599
Dzip1l	0.777927609	-0.9532298	6.57130031	0.0008749
Psmb10	0.993707699	4.30169615	6.54976667	0.0008892
Zfp444	0.868105781	0.92635209	6.54230926	0.0008942
Aif1	0.860436437	1.09802406	6.51938208	0.0009097
Atp6v0c	-0.758033322	2.98434628	-6.4721019	0.0009428
2610001J05Rik	-1.051276517	0.83743215	-6.4190515	0.0009817
Col11a1	-2.178776863	-4.1503905	-6.3718175	0.0010178
Sln2	0.811947424	3.86254422	6.25270547	0.001116
Epsti1	0.945782526	1.74385792	6.1199397	0.0012387
Cd74	1.149751937	8.60950135	6.077981	0.0012807
Psmb9	1.285100988	2.60607071	6.02118849	0.0013402
Cd69	1.005110461	-1.9948003	6.00205474	0.001361
Gm9920	0.796322558	-1.79	5.9620511	0.0014056
Gbp6	1.301405648	1.04793653	5.94181369	0.0014288
H2-M3	0.688716685	3.05296996	5.90479619	0.0014724
Igkv3-1	3.540551628	3.86164515	5.8001152	0.0016045
Gm8909	0.752313445	-0.3811169	5.79179366	0.0016155
Gm5860	0.99572646	-1.5711158	5.70249083	0.0017401
Igkv6-32	3.483451512	4.79377937	5.60525688	0.0018886
Adgre1	0.664192238	4.0363302	5.59058838	0.0019122
Gm17396	-0.837400741	-0.8973363	-5.5735661	0.0019401
Lrp11	-0.862912295	-0.6833083	-5.5654682	0.0019535
I830077J02Rik	1.017890812	-1.2634671	5.55285023	0.0019746
Oas1b	1.109102532	2.39290118	5.48466553	0.0020935
Klrd1	0.860607269	-2.0459467	5.39068851	0.0022712
9930111J21Rik1	0.926966331	-0.5697325	5.36117526	0.0023305

Chadl	-1.40428137	-3.1477004	-5.3089623	0.00244
Draxin	1.07225828	-3.6198337	5.30026868	0.0024587
Podnl1	0.96568481	-0.523224	5.29331464	0.0024739
2010109I03Rik	1.564667609	-4.6923516	5.28514699	0.0024918
Hmgb1-ps9	1.628567032	-2.713226	5.19394495	0.0027026
Ccl5	1.467506544	2.46772335	5.18869162	0.0027154
B2m	0.885451694	11.4768514	5.17885605	0.0027395
Tmem140	0.803021504	1.28302354	5.17043364	0.0027603
Cxcr6	1.109003448	0.40462152	5.15702728	0.0027938
Cdca7l	0.734638089	1.25720894	5.15100659	0.002809
Slc37a2	-0.621833929	-0.389266	-5.1191774	0.0028909
Sp110	1.102615982	0.12139272	5.10543837	0.0029271
Irf7	1.879211199	2.44141085	5.05781502	0.0030567
Gm37008	1.490611625	-0.7602344	5.05524417	0.0030639
Kcnu1	0.994116122	-2.8063345	5.04327647	0.0030976
Tlr13	0.65156631	1.67236533	5.02226804	0.0031578
Tap1	1.028734806	2.4739826	5.00098855	0.0032202
Rab2b	0.804536044	0.46301425	4.97129778	0.0033095
1700112J16Rik	-0.766931757	-1.3501697	-4.9421735	0.0034
Vav2	-0.768132284	3.4142696	-4.9407784	0.0034044
Gm13568	-1.473694296	-0.377657	-4.9308663	0.0034359
Trim34b	0.777441437	-0.2896414	4.92738151	0.003447
Tmem164	-1.188176083	2.94318383	-4.9266127	0.0034495
H2-Q2	0.793462787	4.00167057	4.9184843	0.0034757
Trpv1	-0.955969305	-5.4807084	-4.888774	0.0035734
Cyp2ab1	-1.1140216	-4.0917962	-4.8630997	0.0036603
Mtus2	-1.28560192	-4.5750206	-4.8237312	0.0037984
Oas1c	0.69868534	0.87872457	4.78058066	0.0039567
Irgm1	1.26787736	3.30954334	4.76192366	0.0040274
Trpc3	-0.960192666	-2.4231519	-4.7509813	0.0040696
Sectm1b	2.082088297	-0.7259335	4.72770478	0.0041611
Apol9b	1.050822964	-0.4982787	4.71048739	0.0042302
Polr2k-ps	-1.289302621	-0.5606398	-4.7060688	0.0042482
Apof	1.904065967	6.22923352	4.69397353	0.0042978
Gm29200	1.523898765	-0.9811798	4.68509375	0.0043346
Misp	0.683371273	-2.9119449	4.66585979	0.0044157
Ddx60	1.332935321	-0.538868	4.66048963	0.0044386
Cd40lg	1.813065749	-1.738626	4.6436795	0.0045113
Gsdmd	0.736081563	3.8104693	4.64174143	0.0045198
Fhad1	-0.899533835	-4.3948836	-4.6206628	0.004613
Cd276	0.741346557	0.18776147	4.61056743	0.0046585
H2-DMb2	1.138449128	2.76202736	4.56467542	0.0048717
C920025E04Rik	0.632701936	3.12985962	4.55944468	0.0048967
Vstm2b	-2.114067936	-4.5925858	-4.5583155	0.0049021
Ms4a4b	1.04717713	-0.5748611	4.55178917	0.0049336
R74862	0.777117957	-2.0441758	4.54730361	0.0049553

Dhx58	1.025264658	1.04921187	4.52669993	0.0050566
Gm37969	-2.126686328	-3.4569566	-4.5171073	0.0051046
Il12rb1	0.922899587	-0.7585888	4.51620861	0.0051091
Lgals7	0.755241191	0.38341456	4.49172931	0.0052341
Gm43667	-0.652339606	0.60818131	-4.477406	0.0053088
H2-Aa	0.714687542	6.20045775	4.45655443	0.0054197
Gm14322	-0.90208895	-0.1524746	-4.4560869	0.0054223
Ctsw	0.871996775	0.47760654	4.44980175	0.0054562
Batf2	1.679100824	-1.6081758	4.42983685	0.0055658
Fam221b	-1.524246731	-3.1964203	-4.4146343	0.0056509
Il23r	1.295474691	-4.4876006	4.38539238	0.0058189
Ncf4	0.640532475	1.56013647	4.36416715	0.0059444
Sectm1a	1.98871644	1.25149677	4.36085491	0.0059642
Ankrd22	-0.654806734	-1.0065278	-4.3157729	0.0062422
Mkxn1-ps1	-1.094370881	-3.981349	-4.3063891	0.0063019
Gpr65	1.030530445	1.67122794	4.30523011	0.0063093
H2-DMb1	1.262816999	2.81748585	4.30093869	0.0063369
Gm43128	-1.716412231	-3.2252089	-4.2994018	0.0063468
Cd274	0.836106213	1.62157469	4.29822331	0.0063544
Ciita	0.866052053	1.94609203	4.28527977	0.0064386
Gpr173	-1.443398485	-2.4896416	-4.261267	0.0065982
Tmigd1	-1.368879662	-3.0881942	-4.2289137	0.0068205
RP24-157O12.2	-1.142589999	1.37461434	-4.2249738	0.0068481
Csf3r	0.694046943	0.20317941	4.175759	0.0072044
Psmb8	0.921992992	3.89345623	4.16818373	0.0072611
Gm16093	0.766912867	-2.4189129	4.158627	0.0073333
Timp1	1.040799199	1.31622065	4.14153186	0.0074646
Wars2	1.27077018	-0.1877126	4.11620383	0.007664
Rtp4	1.319273338	3.44560754	4.10660398	0.0077412
Syt17	-1.603805453	-3.3073977	-4.1028481	0.0077716
H2-Ab1	0.997756279	6.21923172	4.10180918	0.0077801
Gm7609	1.081091955	-3.4305159	4.10113801	0.0077856
Cmpk2	1.244285111	2.44919366	4.10111683	0.0077857
Lair1	0.757508326	-0.9706645	4.09228849	0.0078579
Ms4a7	0.736841749	0.98139093	4.08305707	0.0079343
Gpr35	1.059892158	-2.0827064	4.07326893	0.0080161
Cfap126	-1.122149963	-3.1356546	-4.0715595	0.0080305
Mcpt4	-1.606199458	1.06660893	-4.0545033	0.0081758
Pon3	0.705773314	2.44000693	4.03417689	0.0083528
Trpm2	1.044060666	-1.0598422	4.02912238	0.0083975
H2-DMa	0.990819695	3.61772119	4.02193447	0.0084615
Ms4a6d	0.81872051	2.75749084	4.00058778	0.0086549
Lrch2	-0.63233021	-2.0048307	-3.9966342	0.0086913
C920021L13Rik	1.07437364	-2.846482	3.99021918	0.0087506
4633401B06Rik	-0.942561578	-2.0170168	-3.9645466	0.0089929
Ntf5	0.643984915	0.38895321	3.96092992	0.0090277

Cd8b1	1.614057524	-1.0524116	3.94800216	0.0091531
Cyp4f18	0.707120907	1.07356699	3.94528728	0.0091797
Oas1g	1.552000257	-0.126362	3.93673194	0.0092641
Il18bp	1.244654276	3.89925151	3.93530954	0.0092782
9230109A22Rik	2.736098428	-2.4402402	3.93096558	0.0093214
Aoah	0.967268092	0.48131359	3.92948343	0.0093362
Ighj1	1.810322802	1.98911331	3.91975215	0.0094341
Prex1	0.686841573	1.11690294	3.8997486	0.009639
Clec7a	0.778435671	1.00724151	3.89622501	0.0096756
RP24-441E15.4	-1.909437193	-3.3022942	-3.8930245	0.009709
Gm37581	-0.633329208	-0.0269377	-3.8912495	0.0097276
Csl	1.012867242	-3.4188456	3.87525189	0.0098968
Gm9922	1.065416216	0.23501958	3.85378372	0.0101292
Ubd	1.169442941	0.30443084	3.85066875	0.0101634
Klrk1	0.848923515	-2.1939903	3.84377347	0.0102397
Parp14	0.839087118	2.90897114	3.8300929	0.0103928
Rassf9	0.589252073	1.71195858	3.8209046	0.0104972
Gpr141	0.954515008	-1.7403324	3.77850959	0.0109941
Uba7	0.81248292	1.80546863	3.77127909	0.0110815
C1qb	0.611912139	6.51758727	3.74508787	0.0114046
Gm5431	0.937114673	-1.3512154	3.73184588	0.011572
Slc11a1	0.604449196	1.09169728	3.70582334	0.0119092
Ctss	0.832225867	5.91973197	3.69704335	0.0120254
Il2rg	0.894876663	1.85681874	3.68912654	0.0121313
Gm27000	-1.292698451	-0.435484	-3.6888692	0.0121348
4933439K11Rik	-0.594660789	-0.845056	-3.6869137	0.0121611
Parp12	0.69186337	3.19609374	3.68681852	0.0121624
Il7r	1.275822537	0.13913741	3.68277736	0.012217
Serpina3g	0.920321772	2.11799068	3.67919124	0.0122657
Igsf6	0.741091261	1.44982047	3.6784961	0.0122752
Luzp2	-2.065924394	-3.7515888	-3.674104	0.0123352
Trex1	1.174948889	0.5566691	3.66042938	0.0125241
Inpp4b	0.99491188	-1.6559896	3.66002478	0.0125298
Pydc3	0.764030308	-2.7654435	3.63719997	0.0128526
Oas1a	1.308284521	1.99475164	3.63681413	0.0128581
H2-T24	0.752745731	0.81561261	3.63427724	0.0128946
Gm20427	-1.266470659	2.78644989	-3.6274119	0.0129939
Pirb	0.713905255	1.19369497	3.62570946	0.0130186
Gal3st1	-1.502015863	-3.6384984	-3.6223962	0.013067
Gm13421	-0.711421356	-0.2141144	-3.6200436	0.0131014
A530084C06Rik	0.640057878	-1.2681127	3.61876125	0.0131202
Ms4a6c	0.820486831	3.6062573	3.60819022	0.0132765
Ifih1	0.705689541	1.45585103	3.60503351	0.0133235
Vcam1	0.807008364	2.44234503	3.60449141	0.0133316
Gm38375	1.402837035	-2.2175395	3.58846022	0.0135737
Oasl2	1.492439794	2.00148387	3.58571639	0.0136157

Ppapdc3	-1.481271423	-1.1890792	-3.5773772	0.013744
Rgs1	0.783613329	-3.0330451	3.57705026	0.0137491
Gm4841	1.786844984	-0.7804428	3.57039125	0.0138526
Rab19	0.952910485	1.22147105	3.56812038	0.013888
Igf2	-1.058361669	-1.8165575	-3.5667983	0.0139088
Cacna1c	-1.311322039	-1.1788356	-3.5597639	0.0140195
Gm17484	-1.396618694	-3.5521246	-3.5591349	0.0140295
P2ry13	0.743500263	-0.4172273	3.54286199	0.0142898
Kcnd3	-1.872056867	-2.0570219	-3.5408733	0.014322
Plcb2	0.832824173	-0.6437944	3.53839728	0.0143622
Dnd1	-0.72551841	-3.2346919	-3.5224989	0.0146232
Oasl1	1.184447807	0.13541768	3.51969872	0.0146697
Stc1	-0.920269914	0.32313454	-3.5123952	0.0147919
Plek	0.738214244	1.38467558	3.50775193	0.0148701
Ly9	1.054076736	0.4354229	3.50531654	0.0149113
8430432A02Rik	0.893740141	-0.7650364	3.50474584	0.014921
Dsel	0.807623419	-0.4924006	3.49604282	0.0150695
H2-BI	1.004180487	-1.8490199	3.49319337	0.0151185
Usp18	1.429444076	2.20984466	3.48755615	0.0152159
Itgal	1.104761858	0.74650842	3.48383305	0.0152806
Gm2539	-1.150916627	-4.2998576	-3.4835268	0.0152859
Gpx1	1.18899588	5.81184945	3.48247453	0.0153043
Gm16365	-1.761134401	-2.7139336	-3.4822103	0.0153089
Arhgap15	0.876667396	-1.0940145	3.47900665	0.0153649
Fam65c	0.611784554	-3.0967973	3.4772912	0.015395
Cd8a	1.682052778	-2.1709176	3.47692368	0.0154015
Zbp1	1.406480405	1.37117319	3.47686029	0.0154026
2810455O05Rik	-1.378557494	-2.7319045	-3.4730432	0.0154699
Slfn1	1.011224425	0.94595104	3.47172436	0.0154932
Ly86	0.616309687	3.99571323	3.46183596	0.0156693
Slc15a3	0.747860665	-0.0228356	3.46135681	0.0156779
Ankrd34a	-1.080785525	-3.4918775	-3.4535414	0.0158187
Zfp385c	1.141592511	-3.679285	3.45081984	0.0158681
Gm5741	-1.340078443	-0.3850351	-3.4474164	0.0159301
Cysltr2	0.920283451	-2.1668163	3.44635835	0.0159495
Zmynd15	0.764721099	-0.5536066	3.4399803	0.0160665
Il2rb	0.976441369	1.24347014	3.43941472	0.016077
1700040L02Rik	-1.727939486	-1.88936	-3.4219754	0.0164022
Slamf1	1.448734788	-2.9076119	3.42180017	0.0164056
Sit1	1.807072849	-1.7913646	3.42129036	0.0164152
AB124611	0.855898799	0.73892142	3.41259893	0.0165802
Iigp1	1.589790261	4.18068575	3.41121188	0.0166067
Alpk2	0.648481964	-2.6579007	3.40981889	0.0166333
Ptprcap	1.486141206	2.32580906	3.39967894	0.0168289
Sh2d1a	1.893562555	-3.8917324	3.3893987	0.0170298
RP23-281H4.8	0.905534572	-2.4060304	3.38096782	0.0171965

Gm28177	1.240253995	2.60712045	3.37552767	0.0173051
TremI2	1.048337232	-2.2544983	3.36611727	0.0174947
Plbd1	0.596587049	3.14561599	3.35598385	0.0177015
Gm10785	-0.818163243	-0.9897839	-3.3397586	0.0180383
Nkg7	1.081091176	0.58805467	3.33667432	0.0181031
Fcamr	0.747648436	-2.5818247	3.32784935	0.01829
Sla	0.932909473	0.55303989	3.32538848	0.0183425
Prf1	1.44607988	-1.405156	3.32341075	0.0183849
Ffar3	1.505118949	-0.1651363	3.32207129	0.0184136
Bves	-1.40904422	0.38263031	-3.3213418	0.0184293
Tmem107	0.653830057	0.81520172	3.31800872	0.018501
2900009J06Rik	1.069700347	-2.2314518	3.31733958	0.0185155
Tnfrsf18	1.078505468	-1.2169024	3.31670104	0.0185293
Cdh22	0.910933638	-3.0973442	3.31648704	0.0185339
Shisa8	2.47804143	-2.991739	3.31053414	0.0186631
Rep15	-1.021543635	-2.608796	-3.3090962	0.0186944
Unc13d	0.734428301	-0.5341482	3.30311514	0.0188255
0610039K10Rik	0.639054588	-1.1911599	3.2991334	0.0189133
Aff2	-0.835138931	-2.3530572	-3.296211	0.0189781
Gm26901	1.668004596	-3.9582796	3.29125927	0.0190884
S1pr4	1.058460447	-0.384623	3.29122861	0.0190891
A930018M24Rik	-1.114019751	-3.142539	-3.2871086	0.0191814
Mefv	1.486462203	-2.8805741	3.28481585	0.0192329
Relt	0.797086991	-0.3757755	3.28332495	0.0192666
Nos1	-3.139524728	-4.6549123	-3.2830644	0.0192724
Alkbh2	0.651456029	1.44300322	3.28239962	0.0192875
Gm16537	1.736037043	-2.246808	3.27039282	0.019561
Pnliprp2	1.603354855	-0.0252161	3.26935566	0.0195848
Gm11627	-1.089605425	-0.467857	-3.2665216	0.0196501
Gm11574	0.911517349	-1.6489982	3.26191951	0.0197566
BC023105	1.828075136	1.26251401	3.25879529	0.0198293
Smt3h2-ps	0.961900364	-1.8615275	3.24147308	0.0202377
Mb21d1	0.879991662	-2.0083616	3.23989935	0.0202752
A730017C20Rik	-1.674847807	-3.7063832	-3.2392805	0.02029
Adgre4	-0.630106951	-1.6342789	-3.23711	0.020342
Fermt3	0.830358992	2.91869835	3.23610234	0.0203662
Gm38001	1.213894142	-3.7914167	3.2357786	0.020374
Sstr3	1.348809947	-3.2582362	3.23536493	0.0203839
Dgke	0.656454669	-0.7241139	3.23530121	0.0203854
Gm15930	1.507928141	-3.0362628	3.23370352	0.0204239
Xaf1	1.21289802	1.73948206	3.23038787	0.0205039
1700003E16Rik	-1.427807278	-3.843158	-3.2280329	0.020561
Gm43360	-1.113935787	-4.1641467	-3.2278774	0.0205648
Gm42418	0.662377818	5.78507772	3.22733659	0.0205779
1700016A09Rik	1.433463023	-3.1765604	3.22369516	0.0206666
Gm6658	-0.964954678	-0.3079105	-3.2210184	0.020732

1600014C23Rik	0.786947192	-1.4215659	3.21861522	0.020791
2210407C18Rik	1.16044035	5.49388938	3.21715936	0.0208268
Serpinb6c	1.759606258	-3.2053001	3.21669831	0.0208381
Mx2	1.175719475	-0.010022	3.21391956	0.0209067
Gm2396	-0.622635938	-5.9301223	-3.2138716	0.0209079
Mroh7	-1.154630284	-2.8814103	-3.2117626	0.0209601
Gm42809	1.736041423	-1.2772104	3.2109916	0.0209792
Faxc	-1.383548637	-1.4727083	-3.2096198	0.0210133
Gm12185	1.906627881	-1.7595636	3.19969986	0.0212615
Rinl	0.815913765	1.24528683	3.1922319	0.0214506
Gm16731	-0.906909833	0.39378969	-3.1912011	0.0214768
Dsc1	1.008836194	-0.1812608	3.18971397	0.0215147
Bcl2a1d	0.728052983	2.73415187	3.18824812	0.0215522
Slamf8	0.745366781	0.46117237	3.16170101	0.022243
Prrg1	-0.783547021	-3.6608435	-3.1568275	0.0223725
Atp8b5	-1.020315874	-3.6683472	-3.15491	0.0224237
Gm43362	1.06150229	-2.2684507	3.15395614	0.0224492
Igtp	1.369268665	3.65232626	3.15318649	0.0224698
Gm37949	-1.484579083	-3.7086864	-3.1468997	0.0226389
4933406I18Rik	1.490462179	-3.9303128	3.13712565	0.0229046
Tnfaip2	0.737507354	-0.4429646	3.13281281	0.0230229
Ifit1	1.409195614	1.9404498	3.13195353	0.0230465
Fyb	0.726632944	1.88631977	3.12227612	0.0233148
Ighv9-3	2.128475653	6.59143293	3.11516543	0.0235141
H2-T22	0.710277822	1.08275299	3.11269324	0.0235839
Rbm12b1	1.335395807	-2.1869357	3.10714781	0.0237412
Prss12	-1.114076151	-2.8192165	-3.0994802	0.0239605
Tlr9	0.864871083	1.26119431	3.09805852	0.0240015
Cybb	0.641402555	2.7259281	3.09052193	0.0242197
Strip2	0.918452461	-2.1461086	3.088588	0.024276
Elfn2	-1.252321788	-4.1755103	-3.0881633	0.0242884
P2ry1	-0.968757545	-2.2073033	-3.0844498	0.0243971
Gm11642	-0.599262702	0.36658502	-3.0732135	0.0247292
Fgd3	0.720123369	0.35015081	3.07103471	0.0247942
Gm15056	1.295512485	-1.4368676	3.06950495	0.0248399
BC094916	0.889959764	-3.3484715	3.06139747	0.0250839
Stat1	1.001143363	2.76781167	3.05956781	0.0251393
Cabp4	1.843405101	-2.7491195	3.05279841	0.0253455
Bst2	0.903595433	6.14332698	3.0506206	0.0254123
Tgtp1	1.404089874	2.14202526	3.04848677	0.0254778
Slc9a3	-2.102514654	-2.2229713	-3.046681	0.0255335
Serpina3i	0.765370485	-0.6581761	3.04559452	0.025567
Gzma	1.779421642	0.49325904	3.04325569	0.0256394
BC051142	1.652452085	-3.8849093	3.04270038	0.0256566
Slpi	2.095976587	5.04817022	3.04071681	0.0257182
Il27ra	0.69337355	0.28128621	3.03788631	0.0258064

Sirpb1b	1.276530394	-2.8237199	3.03521658	0.0258899
Xirp1	-1.340009649	-4.9289141	-3.035013	0.0258963
Ccr4	1.426285171	-2.9504175	3.03410227	0.0259248
Gbp3	0.662583425	1.35998559	3.03172584	0.0259995
Map3k7cl	-1.650217453	-2.8957449	-3.0308498	0.0260271
Lama3	0.721157847	2.41208037	3.02818628	0.0261112
Gm42590	0.762872266	-0.9345113	3.02785619	0.0261216
Bfsp1	0.639645004	-0.7357867	3.02444581	0.0262297
Nell2	-2.642258469	-3.5840672	-3.0207549	0.0263473
Gm5580	0.730182138	-1.4545444	3.01579969	0.0265061
1810026B05Rik	0.755606282	0.32942344	3.01067771	0.0266713
Cd3g	1.62571314	1.75649845	3.00490714	0.0268589
Dusp2	1.028092414	0.24642513	3.00280155	0.0269276
6030460B20Rik	-1.168551276	-2.6886914	-2.9995834	0.0270332
Kcnb1	-0.979919668	-0.7635499	-2.9990709	0.02705
Pglyrp2	1.098062083	-1.7020589	2.9973035	0.0271082
Rnf213	0.80715571	3.18506519	2.99083765	0.0273222
Fsd1l	-1.138257847	-1.8032799	-2.9795361	0.0277007
Gm26947	1.030386906	-2.4091363	2.96974972	0.0280332
Ccl22	1.566045684	0.13542093	2.95803368	0.028437
Isg15	1.063177144	3.50454798	2.94231407	0.0289889
Tlr8	0.648140302	0.05614015	2.93354847	0.0293018
Klhl15	1.052712883	-1.7740577	2.9289274	0.0294682
Samd4	-0.902117798	0.28938458	-2.9281074	0.0294978
Mmp25	0.839348598	-1.0030872	2.92659067	0.0295527
Itk	0.946724829	-1.0246869	2.92566673	0.0295862
Shisa5	0.71292771	3.40719191	2.9247037	0.0296212
AA386476	0.713392856	-0.2613823	2.92410945	0.0296428
Sowaha	0.777747717	-0.234753	2.90842793	0.0302191
Btnl2	1.648105045	-4.776368	2.90833273	0.0302226
Fasl	1.5439194	-2.4793577	2.90658043	0.0302878
Cd6	1.492432674	-0.9051092	2.90041223	0.0305184
Gm9899	-1.717871194	-3.7259159	-2.8961012	0.0306807
Fam134c	0.921042839	2.8303783	2.89600358	0.0306844
Gm20503	0.625618025	2.13224359	2.89575714	0.0306937
A930024N18Rik	0.931151732	-3.0362822	2.8947459	0.0307319
RP24-470M22.10	-0.609857366	0.40362208	-2.8841546	0.0311355
Herc6	0.910819839	0.86835433	2.88380847	0.0311488
Pld4	0.610471364	4.23314979	2.88029007	0.0312842
Irf5	0.719631151	1.92408991	2.8784911	0.0313536
Dfna5	-1.321634942	-5.0733962	-2.8738281	0.0315345
Slc28a2	0.63755577	-0.8531195	2.87342933	0.0315501
Nptx2	-0.853667778	2.40169977	-2.8731789	0.0315598
Gm36527	1.258394616	-4.0667614	2.8723866	0.0315907
Irgm2	1.188612081	3.08150041	2.86929701	0.0317114
Stat2	0.83324813	4.9339588	2.86516429	0.0318737

Exoc3l2	-0.950606856	-0.5265388	-2.8638902	0.0319239
Tbx18	-1.168680512	-4.3971714	-2.8595573	0.0320953
Gm12216	0.771445688	0.70928551	2.85667769	0.0322097
Gm14085	0.633250284	-2.2223843	2.853214	0.032348
Nptx1	-3.766684545	-3.3581722	-2.8379828	0.0329638
Mfap4	-0.662722786	2.4002995	-2.8336123	0.0331429
Gm37447	0.635196281	-1.8233882	2.83318244	0.0331606
Tbc1d10c	0.92660879	1.62272538	2.83142002	0.0332331
Ii20rb	0.625530128	-1.9843142	2.83122315	0.0332412
Creb5	1.311838269	-3.4336676	2.83016156	0.033285
Ube2l6	0.711273032	1.91627779	2.8264731	0.0334377
Gm17029	-0.758995491	-1.1740547	-2.821369	0.0336502
Gm5148	0.591851444	-3.2441009	2.81292439	0.0340051
Itgb2	0.730746768	2.93881175	2.81193869	0.0340468
Scml4	0.977538864	-1.4674452	2.81048399	0.0341084
Capn8	-1.006780376	-4.8867314	-2.8044211	0.0343665
Art2a-ps	1.651044995	1.21817269	2.80134465	0.0344983
Gm26660	-1.057346757	-3.1477474	-2.7952793	0.0347598
Rad54b	1.720151763	-3.4538968	2.79366499	0.0348298
Gm14418	-1.204677569	-1.6426497	-2.7893104	0.0350192
Sp140	0.817661894	0.07813461	2.78786722	0.0350823
Mex3b	-1.122802678	-1.0327958	-2.7854024	0.0351902
Tmem168	-0.69827311	1.98369165	-2.785175	0.0352002
Ffar2	1.079773513	-0.3990021	2.78260327	0.0353133
Ngf	-0.889720186	0.08341617	-2.7823246	0.0353256
Kmo	0.662447394	-2.0692323	2.78185619	0.0353462
Slit2	-0.736265918	-3.0820934	-2.7812002	0.0353751
Nrep	-0.704553905	2.13765023	-2.7793919	0.035455
Laptm5	0.606871543	3.52708525	2.77866488	0.0354872
Ighv1-64	4.511963343	4.07844782	2.77268039	0.0357533
Irx3os	0.962279151	-3.9382985	2.77077659	0.0358384
Fam169b	1.037204705	-1.7799913	2.76814756	0.0359562
Prr29	1.100246219	-5.105103	2.76767394	0.0359775
Ddx43	1.529005029	-2.2291437	2.76586487	0.0360589
Selplg	0.680246537	1.79539	2.76476863	0.0361084
E130208F15Rik	0.648946683	-0.7723907	2.76258327	0.0362071
4930547M16Rik	1.004124889	-2.7839813	2.76001157	0.0363237
C030037D09Rik	0.88095048	1.11234115	2.75789854	0.0364198
Gm4134	0.879386144	-0.3471041	2.75273381	0.0366559
Tnfrsf4	1.034280673	0.14601544	2.74578623	0.0369761
Tnfrsf22	-0.63318457	-2.1359423	-2.7431264	0.0370995
Htr1b	-2.098226515	-2.7318398	-2.7393119	0.0372772
Glipr1	1.019335316	1.41412015	2.73415896	0.0375188
Cxcl13	1.315619461	5.93221347	2.73258844	0.0375927
Rasgrp1	0.881892885	-0.8353976	2.73228588	0.037607
Rgn	-1.363454794	-2.8608526	-2.7320091	0.0376201

Tm6sf1	0.601117014	0.36882438	2.72827609	0.0377967
Tmem150b	2.17463775	-3.3969002	2.72821831	0.0377994
Napsa	0.722047871	1.76760114	2.72412068	0.0379943
Fgf9	-1.686124232	-2.9442394	-2.7180861	0.0382833
Soat2	1.372235602	-2.9554889	2.71353157	0.038503
Ccdc184	-1.609098716	-3.6067047	-2.7080738	0.0387681
Peg12	-0.757282103	-2.4160958	-2.7076446	0.038789
Scnn1b	-1.182308599	-2.0158593	-2.7046474	0.0389355
Arl5c	0.834278668	-0.6107462	2.70221673	0.0390548
RP23-370A2.5	-0.767061418	-0.5335134	-2.7011824	0.0391057
Acta1	-0.774618335	7.13634948	-2.6995288	0.0391871
C530005A16Rik	-1.19098128	-2.1573783	-2.6992221	0.0392023
Tnfrsf13b	0.974562845	0.45670767	2.69917524	0.0392046
Gm26699	-1.289554589	-3.9379831	-2.6954199	0.0393904
H2-Q4	0.622279146	4.87770257	2.69395171	0.0394633
Zfp442	-0.632101875	-0.1019815	-2.6934746	0.039487
Col8a1	-1.269397183	-1.1688912	-2.6905733	0.0396316
Melk	1.511698033	-0.9485314	2.6892004	0.0397002
Gbp2	0.734655093	3.79981047	2.68552459	0.0398845
Trbc2	1.113918117	1.88939335	2.68081244	0.0401222
Rtn4r	-1.66818802	-1.1756624	-2.6799235	0.0401672
Gm4787	-0.738797201	-1.6426399	-2.6793861	0.0401945
2600006K01Rik	-1.224044978	-1.8019993	-2.6785952	0.0402346
Arhgdib	0.789749682	3.23861975	2.67392492	0.0404724
AW112010	0.743013993	3.89611288	2.66783488	0.0407848
Dnase1l3	0.958211711	0.65773432	2.66216281	0.0410781
Ptma	0.959116526	5.46264228	2.65566544	0.0414169
H19	-1.420406468	-3.5028692	-2.6553913	0.0414313
Spr-ps1	0.767177078	-3.5393423	2.65008583	0.0417103
Rab9b	-1.975607208	-3.8631749	-2.6464062	0.041905
Nmnat2	-1.303847379	-2.9001105	-2.6449467	0.0419825
Irf1	0.677991761	2.65308407	2.6432856	0.0420709
Gsg2	0.823701334	0.96461019	2.63999122	0.0422468
Ppp3cc	0.633984075	1.53969888	2.63442615	0.0425457
Syt15	-1.230156549	-1.3792706	-2.6322826	0.0426615
Ifi44	1.660758241	0.0903043	2.62760692	0.0429152
Doc2b	0.765225817	3.36393773	2.62556179	0.0430266
Gm15775	0.962127472	-2.1116186	2.62229766	0.0432052
Samsn1	0.696581844	-0.984013	2.62091923	0.0432809
1500002C15Rik	-0.78943014	-2.3282056	-2.6201172	0.0433249
Oas3	1.36681089	-1.9603863	2.6158727	0.043559
Myl1	-1.340199927	-3.1480892	-2.6154173	0.0435842
Gm10175	1.100356799	-2.5064987	2.61281501	0.0437285
Gm27030	-0.761020218	-2.2315509	-2.6122437	0.0437603
Tuba8	0.731026843	-0.2381099	2.61067396	0.0438476
Dgki	-0.937974873	-1.2036818	-2.6079969	0.0439971

Ptprz1	-1.251875974	-4.4886268	-2.606904	0.0440582
Fbln7	-1.042313336	-2.6637062	-2.606072	0.0441048
Gpha2	0.878374383	3.73237334	2.60452629	0.0441916
Gm37962	-1.535057889	-2.8459185	-2.6044372	0.0441966
D930048G16Rik	-0.788321239	-2.1801793	-2.5978108	0.0445706
Appbp2os	0.678179061	0.09381352	2.5971796	0.0446064
Amy1	0.722288322	0.85907982	2.59388855	0.0447936
Slc35d3	-1.275898218	-0.9557805	-2.5910272	0.0449571
H2-K1	0.897264125	3.95050603	2.58907907	0.0450687
Fbxl22	-0.613019725	2.1574668	-2.5874145	0.0451644
RP23-288L22.4	-0.730109272	-1.4886603	-2.5844853	0.0453332
Gm10638	-0.823091206	-1.1954535	-2.5831638	0.0454096
Ighv3-8	5.534189814	3.54241656	2.58264527	0.0454396
H2-T23	0.647882894	1.91904583	2.58199913	0.045477
Qprt	0.744856842	-1.4947401	2.58106712	0.0455311
Dock2	0.599213317	1.06391212	2.58101524	0.0455341
Gm15753	0.733724575	1.39665098	2.58027546	0.045577
Sash3	0.787958343	1.82815666	2.5784245	0.0456847
Igkv3-4	4.256283971	2.38395678	2.57668009	0.0457864
Tnnc2	-1.450715347	3.41075251	-2.576654	0.0457879
Pcdhgb4	1.402844306	-3.0945439	2.57598806	0.0458268
Slc35f1	-1.463934406	-2.3656614	-2.5693244	0.0462179
Cnn1	-0.619415508	7.72009633	-2.5684561	0.0462692
Smpdl3b	0.660819553	1.34083041	2.56439938	0.0465093
Cobl	-1.21863508	-3.0368244	-2.5626492	0.0466134
Gm16244	-0.868218842	-4.4799001	-2.5614498	0.0466848
Fpr2	0.657401308	0.05596261	2.56027059	0.0467552
Hsf2bp	-1.058897866	-3.4240403	-2.559635	0.0467931
Dpm1	0.586585385	1.40230995	2.55565983	0.0470313
Ighv14-4	3.681164148	2.52936576	2.55282494	0.047202
Igkv9-129	4.320247918	1.46277222	2.55202611	0.0472502
Sh3gl3	-1.101937765	-3.3183645	-2.5501145	0.0473658
Mid1ip1	-0.698530967	1.81000066	-2.5489247	0.0474379
Plxnc1	0.673705137	-0.0353643	2.54745931	0.0475269
Gatm	0.631393646	3.1847485	2.54592419	0.0476203
Gpr171	1.333055944	-0.7841758	2.54338792	0.047775
Gm15677	0.767153859	-3.0521908	2.54207644	0.0478552
Gm11398	0.767153856	-1.7929184	2.54207642	0.0478552
Gtf2ird2	0.827992797	0.53844582	2.53853887	0.0480723
Osm	1.488625728	-2.8423933	2.53578656	0.0482419
Catip	-0.799652192	-3.2068718	-2.5310053	0.0485382
Fcgr1	0.661793157	1.56625726	2.5308584	0.0485473
Gm10499	0.613932154	-1.6399195	2.52967519	0.0486209
Phf11b	0.63692605	1.81482909	2.5292732	0.048646
Ldoc1	1.191757121	0.91049434	2.52766372	0.0487464
Skap1	1.006469454	-2.3658185	2.52708013	0.0487828

Tigd4	0.773131061	-2.3429533	2.52100635	0.049164
Klrb1b	0.628573845	-0.410499	2.52045487	0.0491988
Gm26840	2.310060213	-3.4665613	2.51902369	0.0492891
Lat	1.171327736	-1.0152744	2.51799319	0.0493543
Ncs1	-0.780298867	-0.2087294	-2.5171514	0.0494076
Arl11	0.678767638	0.55443549	2.51709477	0.0494112
Ren1	0.768328517	3.48328188	2.51601233	0.0494798
Mgl2	-0.781585895	0.82408647	-2.5136077	0.0496327
Klri2	1.278003692	-3.8806302	2.51117008	0.0497881
Lcp2	0.745611168	0.58352997	2.50862147	0.0499512

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Klk1	2.393278894	-3.473828	11.2268664	5.57E-05
Slc16a14	-1.618334222	-3.2327493	-8.6584168	0.0002156
Cd244	-1.265988713	-3.1107146	-8.121773	0.0002993
Gm14817	-2.113414039	-1.7018482	-7.8874111	0.0003474
Gm11365	1.525623493	0.23024029	7.67615242	0.0003987
Ighv9-3	-4.519848411	3.2672709	-7.4816013	0.0004539
Fpr2	-2.498751659	-1.5221139	-7.2779698	0.0005215
A530099J19Rik	-1.567877729	-1.6277984	-7.1990225	0.0005508
Abcb4	-1.375214589	-4.0603346	-7.0655503	0.0006048
A530032D15Rik	-1.143044176	-1.3530777	-6.6009616	0.0008479
Kcnu1	1.192206898	-2.7072891	6.51192562	0.0009066
H2-Eb1	-1.332984836	6.8305953	-6.380169	0.0010023
A130010J15Rik	1.294455311	1.02054861	6.3130818	0.0010556
RP24-127M20.8	-2.689942229	-2.1741674	-6.1144541	0.0012336
P2ry10	-1.665336813	-1.9723883	-6.008314	0.0013429
Clec16a	0.802749923	1.96153593	5.76948844	0.0016327
I830127L07Rik	-1.47992089	-2.3100756	-5.7639996	0.0016401
H2-DMa	-1.071393465	2.58661461	-5.7342327	0.0016813
Arhgap4	-0.842078298	-0.9232033	-5.7186027	0.0017034
H2-Ab1	-1.301206098	5.06975053	-5.6909334	0.0017434
Adap2	-0.756773192	1.84637746	-5.6419966	0.0018168
Gimap4	-1.358972691	0.12911528	-5.5876111	0.0019025
Igkv9-124	-3.199843299	-0.021182	-5.5382795	0.0019844
Pde1b	-0.907660051	-0.6577966	-5.4758845	0.0020938
Dusp2	-1.612982468	-1.0741123	-5.4397109	0.0021605
RP23-44G8.1	-1.103487132	-2.6349158	-5.3470494	0.0023426
Trpm2	-1.458491982	-2.3111185	-5.305312	0.0024304
H2-Aa	-1.1078659	5.28918103	-5.2849503	0.0024747
Vtcn1	1.191032783	-0.7392015	5.26864834	0.0025107
Egr2	-1.098506575	-2.2100821	-5.2559259	0.0025393
Cd300lf	-1.090273028	-1.3892213	-5.2437993	0.0025669
H2-DMb2	-1.169793244	1.60790618	-5.2429857	0.0025687
Wdfy4	-0.931397759	0.46740865	-5.2418139	0.0025714
Cd68	0.991768883	3.67524771	5.23517203	0.0025867
Rasgrp3	-0.82408256	-0.0443566	-5.2339869	0.0025895

Serpina3h	-1.165497574	0.16735771	-5.2186678	0.0026252
Tnfrsf14	-0.885029052	1.00358876	-5.2169512	0.0026292
Gm37962	-1.039345397	-2.5980623	-5.1943414	0.002683
Slc25a53	-0.914546827	-2.3219666	-5.1775339	0.0027238
Abi3	-0.792575811	-0.5783578	-5.151946	0.0027874
Ciita	-1.299458174	0.86333692	-5.0957202	0.0029331
Ctla4	-3.801073051	-3.0261975	-5.0915031	0.0029444
Cxcr6	-1.21306614	-0.7564133	-5.0881724	0.0029534
Klhl6	-1.009592967	-0.2737238	-5.0621449	0.0030244
4930471C06Rik	-1.409675724	-0.5907836	-5.0476847	0.0030646
Ptpn22	-1.897851881	-1.4504396	-5.0268095	0.0031239
Dlec1	-0.901891635	-2.3500995	-5.0104487	0.0031713
9930111J21Rik1	-0.905036963	-1.4857342	-5.0012498	0.0031983
Dzip1l	0.669794719	-1.0072962	4.98508592	0.0032463
Gimap3	-1.503009376	0.2993746	-4.9761784	0.0032732
Iglc1	-3.903728426	1.40515824	-4.9665209	0.0033026
Bcl2a1d	-0.796184894	1.97203293	-4.9248018	0.0034331
Lrp8	-1.735391336	-4.1431108	-4.9122023	0.0034737
Ets1	0.752153841	0.07157194	4.90582892	0.0034944
Gm38388	-1.298315689	-3.9291885	-4.8983945	0.0035188
Cd200r3	2.117121316	-5.4959792	4.87224205	0.0036061
Blm	-0.935080168	-2.7444728	-4.8701301	0.0036132
F730043M19Rik	-1.907529714	-2.4090283	-4.8603599	0.0036465
Slamf7	-1.997199589	-1.1799461	-4.8534234	0.0036704
Dock2	-0.721575708	0.4035176	-4.8350275	0.0037346
Gm37621	-2.295274013	-4.1873656	-4.7960721	0.0038748
4930503L19Rik	-0.615272019	0.02213823	-4.7892368	0.0039
Grap2	-1.408838308	-0.6912163	-4.7708881	0.0039687
Gimap7	-1.559080911	-1.4888047	-4.752879	0.0040374
Fmn1l	-0.86160614	1.05760481	-4.7244945	0.0041485
Gm17494	-1.154155714	-5.4019649	-4.7201976	0.0041656
Gm1966	-1.087477378	-0.5951285	-4.7200352	0.0041663
Bank1	-1.117651664	-2.2914379	-4.714601	0.0041881
Hsd17b14	1.024733481	-2.5756039	4.694717	0.0042688
Cxcl9	-2.271629036	1.77437391	-4.6706456	0.0043691
C920021L13Rik	1.192825161	-2.7872562	4.66811115	0.0043798
Plbd1	-0.877790769	2.40842708	-4.6589101	0.0044189
Dock10	-0.755319217	-0.921048	-4.6548325	0.0044364
Akna	-0.793263887	1.43836351	-4.6545529	0.0044376
Qdpr	0.798312785	2.88671127	4.64917408	0.0044607
9930111J21Rik2	-0.70868528	-0.5684557	-4.6433893	0.0044858
Themis	-1.89635433	-4.7224173	-4.6331369	0.0045306
Gm42783	0.869345439	-1.1735739	4.59021959	0.004724
Ercc6l	-1.321982052	-2.4671203	-4.5504492	0.0049116
Pik3r6	-0.647006498	-0.6234964	-4.5470189	0.0049282
AA465934	-1.72108046	-2.6362833	-4.5340057	0.0049917

Siglece	-1.767620168	0.54423995	-4.5176426	0.0050729
Ms4a4b	-1.03908001	-1.6179897	-4.5107244	0.0051076
Gpr65	-1.127524734	0.59220035	-4.5018617	0.0051526
Il2rb	-1.271586896	0.11945601	-4.4897202	0.0052149
Ttc16	-1.148127126	-4.317824	-4.464452	0.0053473
Slamf8	-1.280105094	-0.5515636	-4.4350835	0.0055061
Ccdc88b	-0.99307652	0.51908149	-4.4277061	0.0055468
Ptprc	-1.062247051	0.34961882	-4.4220666	0.0055782
Sh3bp5l	-1.050881518	0.84211028	-4.4069899	0.005663
Gm26631	-1.330728984	-3.1934091	-4.395559	0.0057283
A630001G21Rik	-2.161966658	-3.2961046	-4.3940705	0.0057369
Klra2	-2.030528233	-2.8066008	-4.3858139	0.0057847
Cdca8	-1.079728526	-1.7582629	-4.3654176	0.0059047
Mir142hg	-1.140618963	0.53312936	-4.3639302	0.0059136
Fcamr	1.248523057	-2.3313874	4.34408641	0.0060333
Hpse	0.912757889	1.18390611	4.34267405	0.0060419
Napsa	-1.116415392	0.8483695	-4.3196475	0.0061846
Tbc1d10c	-1.057711044	0.63056546	-4.315823	0.0062086
Klrb1b	-1.640274484	-1.5449232	-4.2902561	0.0063722
St6gal1	-0.594814893	0.7120714	-4.2880439	0.0063866
Cd38	-0.743060602	1.00939468	-4.2878537	0.0063878
Clec9a	-2.329510183	-1.222026	-4.2677656	0.0065202
A430078G23Rik	-2.852881869	-3.3413738	-4.2531006	0.0066188
Gcsam	-1.130474291	-2.3275681	-4.2492387	0.0066451
Ppp1r16b	-0.885288746	-1.0143546	-4.2415173	0.0066979
Gm15697	-1.57514407	-4.14514	-4.2314783	0.0067673
Ptpn7	-0.898270984	-1.5300464	-4.2197315	0.0068496
Ms4a6b	-1.16449335	0.43640857	-4.2163483	0.0068735
Cytip	-0.787393745	0.07086013	-4.2011062	0.0069824
Snx22	-1.04788502	-1.0463352	-4.1872729	0.0070829
Sowaha	1.124387921	-0.0614329	4.17966578	0.0071389
Podnl1	-2.113504423	-2.0628186	-4.1575013	0.0073049
H2-Ob	-1.608252024	-1.6497652	-4.1474981	0.0073812
Zc3h12d	-2.043480025	-1.5380165	-4.1453278	0.0073979
Slc40a1	0.768234023	-1.5123064	4.12627009	0.0075463
Egr1	-0.754278202	0.52807212	-4.1167174	0.0076219
2900009J06Rik	1.329730953	-2.1014365	4.05018938	0.0081733
Cxcl10	-1.602509001	-0.1856845	-4.040705	0.0082555
Aoc2	-0.785311898	-0.6881405	-4.0259592	0.0083852
Glipr1	-0.927147486	0.44087875	-4.0250333	0.0083934
Ighv1-81	-2.667550672	1.91476819	-4.0171242	0.008464
Fcgr4	-2.044548226	1.60008186	-4.0057451	0.0085668
Igkv6-20	-4.607088561	3.6617644	-3.9830645	0.0087759
Gm11427	-1.359065614	-2.2099902	-3.9826456	0.0087798
Clec4a2	-0.870065676	0.3722125	-3.9750855	0.0088508
Gm13139	-1.046814584	-3.3952313	-3.9739605	0.0088614

Kynu	-1.553654996	-3.8959789	-3.9626349	0.0089692
Ighv8-8	-2.443126025	0.16956849	-3.945642	0.0091336
Cd6	-1.953170653	-2.6279109	-3.9322998	0.0092651
Tap1	-0.590930959	1.66414972	-3.9292528	0.0092955
Gm11748	-1.651390189	-3.4863404	-3.9200138	0.0093881
Rabgef1	0.829961615	2.57471484	3.91561044	0.0094327
Lair1	-0.663406842	-1.681122	-3.9116794	0.0094726
Cd74	-1.044394109	7.51242832	-3.9027005	0.0095646
Cd40	-1.05790415	-2.0877285	-3.9024781	0.0095669
C030013C21Rik	-0.964986988	-2.9155311	-3.8873231	0.0097245
Gm15879	1.592332884	-1.9543935	3.88320819	0.0097678
Gm1976	0.598265605	-1.9049035	3.87677726	0.009836
Fcrls	-1.265833049	1.49918443	-3.876238	0.0098417
Lyz1	-1.716648707	1.69870909	-3.8689299	0.0099198
Fam26f	-0.866032993	0.32369905	-3.8575439	0.0100429
Clec4a1	-0.635613958	2.52349819	-3.8555161	0.010065
Akap5	-1.345884014	-4.8030717	-3.8546464	0.0100745
Cd300a	0.859047496	-0.3274333	3.8422464	0.010211
Pax5	-2.396884394	-2.800439	-3.8421931	0.0102116
Fam169b	-1.802413414	-3.1998004	-3.8366367	0.0102734
Gm18953	-0.606822239	1.37545029	-3.8342842	0.0102998
Sla	-1.100534718	-0.4636822	-3.8269576	0.0103822
Gm42648	-1.413222247	-2.6880059	-3.8174279	0.0104905
Hvcn1	-0.914126328	0.47970494	-3.816888	0.0104967
Igll2	-3.231793849	1.04109483	-3.8096603	0.0105798
Arhgap27os2	0.700726515	0.49880483	3.80812566	0.0105975
Havcr2	-0.947505767	-0.7332547	-3.8030869	0.010656
A530084C06Rik	0.71370491	-1.2312892	3.77643656	0.0109714
Gzmm	0.99894653	-2.156094	3.76732168	0.0110817
Trbc1	-1.878528571	-0.263169	-3.7641519	0.0111203
Itgad	-1.996207466	-3.3656575	-3.7614241	0.0111537
Trbc2	-1.089694312	0.78758714	-3.7610267	0.0111586
Btla	-1.560697174	-0.8278528	-3.7478664	0.0113213
Gm14023	-0.702843389	-1.3904743	-3.7443092	0.0113657
Ighv3-6	-3.723107251	1.90491882	-3.7428254	0.0113843
Cd3d	-2.745775503	-1.1748475	-3.7220122	0.0116487
Cacna1e	-2.06776645	-4.8947897	-3.720482	0.0116685
Tmigd1	-0.906372811	-2.8569408	-3.7110487	0.0117908
Rasal3	-1.156497145	-1.2973274	-3.7065397	0.0118498
Cd96	-2.34495946	-3.1550043	-3.6950792	0.0120013
Nkg7	-1.256183361	-0.5805826	-3.6950404	0.0120018
Itgax	-1.023770944	-0.0001163	-3.6889758	0.0120828
Nsl1	-1.47052833	-2.980396	-3.6818519	0.0121788
Il12rb1	-0.918261752	-1.6791694	-3.679805	0.0122065
Rgs16	-1.192188281	-1.0274013	-3.6793952	0.0122121
Ugt1a8	1.939220571	-2.2963041	3.67278977	0.0123021

Serpina3i	-0.9987859	-1.5402543	-3.6681154	0.0123663
E030037K01Rik	1.499029547	-2.581072	3.65792684	0.0125075
Icos	-2.961787372	-2.7593115	-3.6566617	0.0125251
Dsel	0.767002584	-0.5127111	3.65631231	0.01253
Gm12353	-1.24163689	-2.5894706	-3.6512145	0.0126015
Slc9a9	0.613981868	1.57081645	3.64693338	0.0126618
Cd247	-1.69549998	-3.0374926	-3.6413521	0.012741
Iglv1	-3.559400131	3.08551678	-3.6395169	0.0127672
Fgd2	-0.641172479	0.63556862	-3.6386331	0.0127798
Samsn1	-0.780095914	-1.7223519	-3.6150885	0.0131212
Hcls1	-0.751525988	2.46720542	-3.6085411	0.013218
Gimap8	-0.969983568	-0.7389579	-3.5704701	0.0137967
Cd72	-1.409537242	-0.3113784	-3.5652082	0.0138789
Skap1	-2.078785014	-3.9084457	-3.5624696	0.0139219
Fam65b	-1.107468007	-2.0599063	-3.5601398	0.0139586
Myo1g	-0.72926982	0.09131512	-3.5515762	0.0140945
Pmaip1	-0.99366618	0.03054261	-3.5479075	0.0141531
H2-DMb1	-0.712309192	1.82992275	-3.5418191	0.014251
Serpina3g	-1.426241838	0.94470887	-3.5365733	0.014336
Cxcl16	-0.647175861	1.93183325	-3.5303503	0.0144376
Itgb2	-0.662006755	2.24243499	-3.5258055	0.0145123
Bard1	-1.426542866	-2.8571763	-3.5237481	0.0145462
Gm42590	0.708247003	-0.9618239	3.51943361	0.0146177
Ccl5	-1.587833076	0.94005354	-3.5166978	0.0146632
Nrgn	-0.928758518	-1.874719	-3.5123502	0.0147359
Krtdap	1.186584978	-2.2487349	3.50346505	0.0148857
Srgn	-0.61720809	2.30457984	-3.5014867	0.0149193
Ribc1	0.653766559	-0.4916646	3.50139599	0.0149209
A430093F15Rik	-2.192429176	-5.0684119	-3.4993288	0.014956
Ccr10	-2.192429163	-3.4202158	-3.4993288	0.014956
Clcf1	-0.831075692	-1.5010014	-3.4889174	0.0151347
RP23-288L22.4	-1.984731154	-2.1159713	-3.4843536	0.0152138
Gm16712	0.801203993	-2.3340718	3.44261142	0.0159588
Siglecg	-1.33808466	-2.63866	-3.4422127	0.0159661
Chst3	-1.179270745	-2.4665849	-3.4375517	0.0160518
Pcdhga8	-1.109404358	-4.7827314	-3.4373897	0.0160548
Gabra3	0.681733973	-0.7056349	3.43510291	0.0160971
AU020206	-0.878531939	2.56831123	-3.4332958	0.0161306
Tox	-0.679801024	-0.3264061	-3.4276591	0.0162355
Itgam	-1.467041525	1.19117422	-3.4202863	0.0163739
Cysltr2	-1.423318058	-3.338617	-3.407436	0.0166184
Ces2b	1.417178757	-3.7211639	3.40635503	0.0166391
Gm11948	-1.046794742	-0.6547662	-3.397969	0.0168011
Cxcr5	-2.466149563	-2.3207294	-3.3940728	0.0168769
BE692007	-2.958873086	-3.9731649	-3.3937966	0.0168823
Gm37008	0.814936267	-1.0980721	3.39138255	0.0169295

Gm15199	1.531736296	-2.1706071	3.38840156	0.016988
Nedd9	-0.851734716	0.78961764	-3.3861131	0.017033
3110053B16Rik	-0.92749715	-3.305448	-3.3859667	0.0170359
Tm6sf1	-0.674554565	-0.2690114	-3.3859029	0.0170372
Serpina3f	-1.677309438	-1.6683175	-3.3845476	0.0170639
RP23-66E21.1	0.976588793	-0.1811864	3.38166469	0.017121
Gm37699	0.692971692	-1.9363799	3.37534331	0.0172468
Rxfp1	-1.039177947	-1.3603831	-3.3644167	0.0174668
Krt5	0.815243555	4.04687709	3.36354758	0.0174845
2510016D11Rik	0.969237523	-0.2992711	3.36267709	0.0175022
Gm16731	-0.770198649	0.46214528	-3.3595974	0.0175649
Arhgap27os3	-1.46771169	-1.7054641	-3.3528518	0.0177031
Mef2b	-2.160286116	-3.2657352	-3.3439179	0.0178881
A530030E21Rik	-1.844332042	-3.0014112	-3.3399488	0.0179709
Gm26606	-0.863584223	-1.0539748	-3.3277934	0.0182274
A330069E16Rik	0.84104995	-1.2384638	3.32260292	0.0183381
Il9r	-2.222468185	-3.793609	-3.3070352	0.0186748
Aspm	-2.253919884	-3.551171	-3.3027762	0.0187681
Cxcr3	-1.801605145	0.0660687	-3.2980107	0.0188731
Tsc22d3	-0.942359342	2.80168076	-3.296783	0.0189003
Slc13a3	-2.768662309	-3.7304714	-3.2939208	0.0189638
1810034E14Rik	-0.682539786	-2.4713142	-3.2837076	0.0191923
Nubpl	0.612858465	-0.1475552	3.27967944	0.0192832
Dusp1	-0.812477266	1.75645127	-3.2742138	0.0194074
Trim59	-1.066565311	-0.7851459	-3.2672395	0.0195672
D430013B06Rik	-0.963297732	-0.7189074	-3.257957	0.0197821
Itgal	-1.223643749	-0.4176944	-3.2555603	0.019838
Dnase1l3	-2.106905086	-0.8748241	-3.2527317	0.0199042
Il33	0.730999715	1.75160935	3.25142527	0.0199349
BC023105	-1.629735371	-0.4663912	-3.2509436	0.0199462
Klra13-ps	1.399791631	-0.4719922	3.24425582	0.0201041
Ccdc71	1.014877764	1.40729537	3.2394786	0.0202178
Diap2	-0.722710416	-0.5421275	-3.2336494	0.0203574
Ighj4	-2.600663996	1.44889758	-3.2247437	0.0205728
Ighg1	-3.713706899	5.6984179	-3.2221795	0.0206353
Ccl2	-0.843958028	-0.2241997	-3.2041436	0.0210809
Cxcl13	-1.493552492	4.52762749	-3.1993481	0.0212012
Gm29253	5.161443028	-3.9598091	3.19907713	0.021208
Amica1	-1.754572592	1.56109726	-3.1951428	0.0213073
Agap2	-0.616586674	-0.1627662	-3.1743433	0.0218407
Xlr4b	-0.827687943	-2.2887169	-3.1702819	0.0219466
ItpkA	-1.431770677	-2.3471382	-3.1685656	0.0219915
Gm37639	-0.918604382	-3.5525041	-3.1610659	0.022189
Cd2	-1.993892122	-0.8910337	-3.1564506	0.0223115
Cd79b	-2.140363608	0.01624637	-3.1553681	0.0223403
Slamf6	-1.701150589	-2.7432267	-3.1519798	0.0224309

Gm6034	-0.970059341	-1.7466339	-3.151197	0.0224519
Traf3ip3	-0.809986296	-2.1406582	-3.1505701	0.0224687
Ccdc27	-1.631709284	-3.9759557	-3.1494231	0.0224995
Fcho1	-0.787422024	-1.146497	-3.1375399	0.0228213
Fyb	-0.615987744	1.21500943	-3.1372941	0.022828
Pdcd1	-2.363151647	-1.2269665	-3.1357567	0.0228701
Gm16314	0.612697062	0.21869588	3.13535076	0.0228812
Slc22a15	-1.035952077	-3.1779628	-3.1273399	0.0231016
Cnr2	-1.031566375	-1.2186397	-3.1268223	0.023116
Moxd1	0.663714118	0.27756012	3.12469471	0.023175
Timp1	1.950169546	1.77090583	3.12216354	0.0232454
Gpr55	-1.930050517	-2.6448682	-3.1196523	0.0233155
Amn1	-0.743470802	-0.4997388	-3.1154467	0.0234333
Gpr31b	-2.285055513	-2.1943618	-3.1124665	0.0235173
Fam83d	-1.720807401	-2.714923	-3.1049696	0.0237299
Igkv3-1	-0.797690087	1.69252429	-3.1026242	0.0237969
Pemt	0.594770613	-0.7380456	3.09813978	0.0239255
Serpina3n	0.923037789	4.1060034	3.09543626	0.0240034
Ighv1-26	-4.263533522	3.36588236	-3.0884165	0.024207
Tbx18	1.594317163	-3.0156725	3.08736478	0.0242376
9530052C20Rik	0.781639119	-2.2504018	3.08722505	0.0242417
Dcaf17	1.047608665	0.20842152	3.08610872	0.0242743
Efnb3	1.00317621	-1.482099	3.08208993	0.0243921
Igkv4-79	-3.01209666	1.05656478	-3.0811675	0.0244192
Gm26699	-0.965102862	-3.7757572	-3.0780016	0.0245125
Jak3	-0.812581901	0.31324709	-3.0751797	0.0245961
H2-K2	-0.898455917	0.86580067	-3.0727042	0.0246696
C1qtnf3	-0.712253178	-0.0703413	-3.0725467	0.0246743
Jchain	-3.538811032	3.63241317	-3.0677797	0.0248166
Wfdc17	1.482774351	4.09858496	3.06656397	0.0248531
Klra7	1.049579833	-2.0165698	3.06423732	0.024923
Cpne1	-0.95385274	0.57361181	-3.0588995	0.0250842
Slc12a5	-0.639003473	-2.278032	-3.0530349	0.0252626
Pnliprp2	1.564704254	-0.0445414	3.05114014	0.0253205
A930015D03Rik	0.682536789	0.13528567	3.0480451	0.0254155
Mzb1	-4.352603341	1.63527315	-3.0479874	0.0254173
Gm17096	0.701336823	-1.9649976	3.04414124	0.0255359
Myl4	-1.089978825	-3.2704825	-3.0424828	0.0255872
Vcam1	-0.814114881	1.63178341	-3.0364252	0.0257756
Gm37973	-1.160050198	-3.515225	-3.0307125	0.0259547
Ppp1r18os	-0.928123874	-2.0522073	-3.0298003	0.0259834
Ryr1	-1.267846752	-4.9170911	-3.0272759	0.0260631
3222401L13Rik	-0.770211907	-4.2818463	-3.020194	0.0262881
Cmah	-1.238929984	-0.2509567	-3.0193092	0.0263163
Ccdc40	1.037791131	-3.7207292	3.0177117	0.0263674
Stab1	0.710045611	2.32270658	3.0148044	0.0264607

Rasgrp1	-1.092967081	-1.8228276	-3.0041342	0.0268062
Gm14399	-0.844450611	-4.0363836	-3.0021239	0.0268718
Tuba4a	0.64489985	2.96129388	3.00051911	0.0269243
Rgs1	-1.040235835	-3.9449697	-3.000213	0.0269344
Igha	-4.796472177	2.55961072	-2.9996706	0.0269522
Bcl2a1a	-1.469691839	0.12447608	-2.9981687	0.0270015
Rep15	-1.36401273	-2.7800306	-2.9936628	0.02715
Itk	-1.389775788	-2.1929372	-2.9860145	0.0274043
Cd300lb	0.712910204	-0.4297258	2.98344434	0.0274903
Ighv1-74	-3.456225963	0.35693609	-2.9817991	0.0275455
Klhl33	1.180550836	-1.9412624	2.98120657	0.0275654
Ccl28	-1.664087201	-3.1624443	-2.9775842	0.0276875
Fgl2	-0.682540809	3.51262071	-2.9772318	0.0276995
Dgke	0.645128659	-0.7297769	2.96893391	0.0279816
Gm26825	-1.381098238	-1.6240657	-2.9643733	0.028138
Il27ra	-1.869804661	-1.0003029	-2.9610346	0.0282531
Il7r	-0.864363134	-0.9309554	-2.9548319	0.0284683
Errfi1	-0.637398134	3.49346832	-2.9548065	0.0284692
Pcdhgb7	0.641280734	-0.8200807	2.94820149	0.0287003
Hdc	0.633635187	0.93695748	2.94335922	0.0288711
Gm37969	-1.307278707	-3.0472528	-2.9407588	0.0289633
Gm11696	-1.719443285	-3.0379714	-2.9399796	0.028991
Gm26660	-1.261343382	-3.2497457	-2.9363121	0.0291217
Amz1	-0.699833799	-2.2206964	-2.934451	0.0291882
Acap1	-1.667533062	-1.2104318	-2.9229792	0.0296022
Bcl3	-0.71628759	0.40569244	-2.9204613	0.029694
Cd3e	-1.713589318	-0.2700186	-2.9164592	0.0298404
Ms4a6c	-0.612106815	2.88996048	-2.9162736	0.0298472
Pla2g4c	-1.272735023	-3.7220538	-2.9105389	0.0300585
Gm37968	-1.168930903	-2.854062	-2.9095043	0.0300968
Stac3	-0.96528559	-2.8514641	-2.9041189	0.030297
Gm43291	-3.039815366	-3.4977501	-2.9040914	0.030298
Zbtb32	-1.160188255	-2.0045661	-2.9004954	0.0304325
Rac2	-0.967749169	2.63252068	-2.9002077	0.0304433
Ube2v1	-1.359238779	1.19638684	-2.8997826	0.0304592
Tnfrsf18	-0.935102811	-2.2237065	-2.8978273	0.0305327
Fmo3	-1.655469494	-1.9699403	-2.8943269	0.0306647
Al662270	-1.013207049	1.10500598	-2.8935295	0.0306949
Mrpl2	0.731060923	3.0550534	2.88756019	0.0309217
Gm43598	1.091503753	-2.9996207	2.88109769	0.0311693
Hmmr	-2.814115533	-2.787522	-2.8808348	0.0311795
Zfp109	-0.640416481	-1.8921557	-2.8806752	0.0311856
Ptprz1	-0.984257666	-4.3548177	-2.8787351	0.0312604
Aqp3	3.808039771	-1.6836003	2.87803161	0.0312876
Tspan32	-0.834561965	-1.5477379	-2.8761827	0.0313591
Kif21b	-0.9505128	-0.526816	-2.8756609	0.0313793

Ptafr	0.742721222	1.99229216	2.87515638	0.0313989
Hsf5	-0.923321047	-3.5999506	-2.8694782	0.0316201
Zfp541	-1.210607287	-5.3130444	-2.8661622	0.03175
Adat3	0.768269182	0.96162611	2.86484067	0.0318019
Gm21972	1.678322275	-1.01304	2.86366871	0.0318481
Lck	-0.970406299	0.33181595	-2.8558808	0.0321566
Cfap74	-0.585157055	-5.4865063	-2.8417527	0.0327247
Il2rg	-0.689849151	1.06445583	-2.8398827	0.0328007
Trpc4	-1.153997886	-5.4888298	-2.8328696	0.0330874
Nras	-1.06774017	1.26395894	-2.8311889	0.0331566
Ighd	-1.068986017	0.0102196	-2.8237372	0.033465
Al427809	1.238297212	-3.2649233	2.8202679	0.0336096
Arhgap25	-0.844337025	-0.6949817	-2.8165778	0.0337643
Gm11535	0.820383223	2.95559961	2.81252681	0.0339349
Gm26850	0.660800787	-3.4171447	2.81241705	0.0339395
Figl1	-2.116349521	-3.4767737	-2.8052702	0.0342429
Dsc1	1.24332351	-0.0640171	2.80490824	0.0342584
Cd69	-2.472731199	-3.7337211	-2.8046896	0.0342677
Gm18342	-0.669662154	0.0598888	-2.8041642	0.0342901
Capn6	0.731644197	-1.6865592	2.8034122	0.0343223
Egr3	-0.934942738	-1.7203403	-2.8033608	0.0343245
Gm17552	-0.87847124	-2.0991759	-2.8011048	0.0344211
Gm8995	-0.589469387	1.0380775	-2.7998297	0.0344758
G630016G05Rik	-1.072341776	-4.3994997	-2.7938943	0.0347319
Per1	-0.590352092	3.06838861	-2.7869936	0.0350323
Chil3	2.382238191	-0.2810414	2.78652177	0.0350529
Igkv1-117	-4.097298254	0.68381298	-2.7822707	0.0352395
Fhad1	-0.820757229	-4.3554953	-2.7812106	0.0352862
Gm29367	0.952766792	-4.0852288	2.77514474	0.0355547
Mob1a	1.501655891	3.31458894	2.7718855	0.0356998
Amd-ps1	0.635913099	3.1080247	2.77166666	0.0357096
Atoh8	0.79813463	2.57744027	2.76987884	0.0357895
4930519P11Rik	-1.487502065	-1.4598085	-2.7689418	0.0358315
Gpr171	-1.72250113	-2.3119543	-2.7688995	0.0358334
Adgrl3	-0.707589435	-3.3830189	-2.7646589	0.036024
Spn	-1.487025758	-0.0424876	-2.7643718	0.036037
Klra10	1.100308433	-1.0710533	2.76285058	0.0361056
Bin2	-0.784166812	0.26255058	-2.7490043	0.0367373
Foxp3	-2.127095213	-3.5297313	-2.7489439	0.0367401
Recql4	-1.627833067	-3.2274353	-2.7480187	0.0367828
Lag3	-1.656799639	-0.6547427	-2.7447453	0.0369341
Pilra	-1.221572545	-2.4895359	-2.7437786	0.0369789
Lat2	-0.912942496	-0.5166947	-2.7427654	0.0370259
Cd79a	-1.902275908	1.11216367	-2.7405842	0.0371274
Nr3c2	0.650402308	0.10238717	2.74014097	0.037148
Ptprcap	-1.113504845	1.02598604	-2.7398066	0.0371636

Itga4	-0.897262961	-0.2654571	-2.738473	0.0372259
RP23-436D14.6	-0.760174795	-1.7323659	-2.7326437	0.0374993
Gm13154	-0.701353819	-2.6542015	-2.7317959	0.0375392
Cd86	-0.692647904	-0.05602	-2.731748	0.0375415
Igkv5-45	-3.238672078	1.70799108	-2.7288032	0.0376806
Gm16286	1.216032266	2.56940348	2.72682771	0.0377743
Lgals3	0.731760167	2.66610836	2.72476195	0.0378725
Cd300ld	-0.764999663	-1.3082123	-2.7180682	0.0381926
Hbb-bt	-1.092360158	3.26472229	-2.7129746	0.0384382
Gm15848	1.108430485	-1.4192192	2.71195065	0.0384877
Mboat4	0.740946602	-0.6613349	2.71098788	0.0385344
Gm2238	1.531784899	-5.2629383	2.705984	0.038778
H2-M2	-1.810548243	-1.4787142	-2.6985811	0.0391414
4921507P07Rik	-0.65210066	-1.7148172	-2.6985302	0.0391439
Rinl	-0.689906653	0.49237662	-2.6976535	0.0391872
3110083C13Rik	1.306088858	-2.4148093	2.69529635	0.0393038
Ccr7	-1.887644586	-1.7767762	-2.6935653	0.0393897
Insrr	-0.664810759	-2.4519593	-2.6919497	0.0394701
Cep55	-1.245642309	-1.5548684	-2.6898973	0.0395724
Gm12454	-1.465945729	-0.6680277	-2.688909	0.0396218
Igkc	-3.046412506	8.27109391	-2.6863663	0.0397491
Trac	-1.55421672	0.15800032	-2.685473	0.039794
Map4k1	-0.961481539	0.72453663	-2.6851066	0.0398124
Eomes	-1.444367448	-4.843261	-2.6833499	0.0399008
Gm38375	1.149548904	-2.3441835	2.68289919	0.0399235
Bcl2l1	0.928228794	1.11854061	2.68105651	0.0400165
Gm11946	-1.489712117	-0.5801101	-2.6783082	0.0401557
Hcst	-1.524584071	-0.9985298	-2.6776052	0.0401914
Rcsd1	-0.810747567	-0.4061711	-2.6768485	0.0402298
Ighm	-1.810759896	6.10901261	-2.6715849	0.0404983
Gcnt4	-1.996624364	-3.4767261	-2.6661011	0.0407801
AI504432	-1.148551092	-1.2195689	-2.6569658	0.0412543
Cpa3	1.019453028	1.33628905	2.65630853	0.0412887
Appbp2os	0.716132689	0.11279033	2.653429	0.0414395
Vkorc1l1	-0.614880418	2.0752031	-2.6490083	0.0416723
Cxxc4	0.726226693	0.65862202	2.64484775	0.0418926
Ncapg	-1.57014069	-3.7117319	-2.6417386	0.0420581
Cldn12	0.828969221	0.20632779	2.64108744	0.0420928
Igkv6-23	-4.579779948	1.82980901	-2.6406182	0.0421179
Lrrc73	-0.704894445	0.94728798	-2.6368229	0.0423212
Phf11a	-0.840534577	-0.8128794	-2.6366416	0.0423309
Gm21985	0.758200346	-3.9859879	2.63366341	0.0424912
Col3a1	0.871850035	4.50645952	2.63042649	0.0426662
Matk	-0.762370853	-2.704823	-2.6302227	0.0426772
Evi2a	-0.688080792	-0.0663743	-2.619485	0.0432634
Map3k7cl	0.969163109	-1.5860546	2.61859681	0.0433122

4933408B17Rik	-1.460412089	-4.2573642	-2.6177744	0.0433576
Gm26779	-0.760013631	0.80327563	-2.6170951	0.043395
Gm28875	0.670458369	-1.1226467	2.61631874	0.0434379
P2ry14	-0.595988741	-3.7249782	-2.6133719	0.043601
C1qtnf5	1.047624361	-1.7333979	2.60718023	0.0439458
E130102H24Rik	-0.640622154	2.35423788	-2.6049446	0.044071
A630033H20Rik	-0.603458292	-3.512084	-2.6048315	0.0440774
Tespa1	-1.61132857	-1.9739747	-2.6026745	0.0441986
Diras2	-0.949383566	-3.0724	-2.6004206	0.0443256
RP23-84M17.5	-1.298397482	-4.5132729	-2.600416	0.0443259
Abca13	0.814975886	-7.0589439	2.60008441	0.0443446
Ager	-0.827073612	-2.0706261	-2.5989296	0.0444099
Ms4a14	0.890794627	-2.6365711	2.59769197	0.04448
Lax1	-2.190945064	-0.2181275	-2.5976061	0.0444848
Lilr4b	0.651144787	1.06800967	2.5937677	0.0447029
Runx3	-1.096584487	-1.5627527	-2.5905859	0.0448846
Gm4759	-0.676010503	0.17296619	-2.5892351	0.044962
Kcna3	-1.0469283	-1.5973591	-2.5880616	0.0450293
Gbp8	-1.832837997	-1.1775713	-2.5838076	0.0452743
Tnfsf8	-1.464770268	-2.2019466	-2.5817128	0.0453954
Gm14634	0.801216226	-2.8752098	2.58043107	0.0454697
Plin2	0.646651848	1.61551372	2.57665347	0.0456895
Adamtsl2	-1.405767151	-5.7582708	-2.5754647	0.0457589
Tmem151b	-1.034504663	-3.2754744	-2.5729391	0.0459067
9230109A22Rik	1.922762982	-2.8469079	2.56526579	0.046359
Dlgap5	-1.567666667	-3.2570896	-2.5599397	0.0466757
Gucy1a2	1.091435295	-2.9069923	2.55765722	0.0468121
Mki67	-1.564974264	0.03904825	-2.5572514	0.0468365
Arhgap30	-0.595871862	0.73915639	-2.5546943	0.0469899
Tgtp1	-1.418007054	0.73097679	-2.5538877	0.0470384
Slpi	-2.626363491	2.68700018	-2.5520971	0.0471463
Lyn	-0.604814104	2.11840598	-2.547157	0.0474454
Gm15987	-1.691965421	-2.2667001	-2.5468823	0.0474621
6030445D17Rik	1.713292985	-2.8910737	2.5445802	0.0476022
Gm43300	-0.828997674	-0.0817846	-2.5391995	0.0479314
Cd274	-0.704455781	0.85129369	-2.5357522	0.0481437
Vav1	-0.596979413	0.65702988	-2.5353806	0.0481666
Cd27	-1.81030272	-2.9834827	-2.5353563	0.0481681
Nhej1	0.585927867	0.37150226	2.53511235	0.0481832
Cenpa	-1.137487243	-1.935785	-2.5337644	0.0482665
Rab2b	0.610375389	0.36593392	2.53207902	0.0483709
Gm26514	-1.119594927	-1.5619673	-2.5311385	0.0484293
Ctsw	-0.919875844	-0.4183298	-2.5308597	0.0484466
Igkv2-109	-3.60129544	-0.3144728	-2.5275308	0.0486539
Dyx1c1	-0.908346726	-3.4613223	-2.5269109	0.0486926
Rab37	-0.998548374	-2.782495	-2.5257804	0.0487633

Ctgf	-0.764937403	3.64522622	-2.5257803	0.0487633
Klra8	1.219203833	1.21472838	2.52356955	0.0489018
Klra17	-1.882873208	-2.3107206	-2.5169997	0.0493159
Cma1	1.109379497	1.63865804	2.51230723	0.049614
Gm5741	-1.544194593	-0.4870932	-2.510976	0.049699
RP23-349I9.14	-1.436845025	-2.7127677	-2.5108084	0.0497097
Gm27011	1.46776229	-2.0454916	2.51012425	0.0497534
Sh2d5	-0.631760877	-3.8586813	-2.5094994	0.0497934
Gm8989	-1.381349912	-4.3161944	-2.5087024	0.0498444

Note: Experimental autoimmune prostatitis